

Subsidized Organic Groceries
Kanaleneiland Utrecht
By “Duurzaam Utrecht 2030”

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Mission and vision of “Duurzaam Utrecht 2030”

Mission

The mission of the Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 is to allow Utrecht residents with little money to participate in a Sustainable and climate-neutral Utrecht for 2030 according to their own insights, in consultation and cooperation with the municipality of Utrecht and other authorities, social organizations, educational institutions, companies and fellow citizens. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations are central to this, from poverty reduction to combating climate change.

Vision

The vision is to become a vibrant, sustainable, and climate-neutral city by 2030, achieved through the active participation of all its citizens, businesses, and organizations. This transformation is based on a shared commitment where each individual, community, and organization contribute in their own unique way, aligned with their abilities, needs, and aspirations. By embracing inclusivity, “Duurzaam Utrecht 2030” aims to create a sustainable future that reflects the diversity of its people and respects the varying contributions they can make. By taking into account everyone’s wishes and capabilities, Utrecht will become a model city where sustainability is not just a goal but a collective lifestyle. It will prioritize the well being of future generations, a clean and healthy environment, and the resilience of its communities in the face of climate challenges.

Context of the Trial

This report presents the results and analysis of the “Organic Subsidized Groceries” project conducted in the Kanaleneiland district. The project ran from May 2024 and was led by Ineke Malsch, founder of the “Duurzaam Utrecht 2030” organization, along with Noor Ul Ain, an intern from Aeres University of Applied Sciences who joined in March 2024. This initiative followed a previous trial of subsidized organic groceries in Lunetten in 2023, which stemmed from research titled 'Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 - Subsidizing Organic and Sustainable Fruit and Vegetables' by Jinte van Eijk, Teun Hartstra, Tymen Swets, Niels Hoevenberg, and Maud Rampaart, Environmental Science students at HAS University of Applied Sciences. These students proposed several options to provide local residents with sustainable groceries on a tight budget, one of which involved using municipal subsidies to purchase vouchers at the organic supermarket such as Ekovers in the Lunetten district.

Building on the insights gained from the Lunetten trial, the Kanaleneiland trial aimed to explore the feasibility and impact of expanding the subsidized organic groceries initiative to another district. The objective was to assess whether similar benefits could be observed and to identify any unique challenges or opportunities presented by the new location. Throughout the project, a diverse range of data was collected, including quantitative metrics on grocery purchases and qualitative feedback from participants.

This report outlines the key findings from the feedback and interviews collected, along with potential solutions and recommendations for other organizations, local businesses, and the municipality of Utrecht.

In addition to the core findings, the report highlights several key recommendations for scaling the initiative further. By presenting a detailed account of the Organic Subsidized Groceries project in Kanaleneiland, this report seeks to contribute to the broader discussion on sustainable urban food systems and the role of municipal support in promoting healthy, organic eating habits among all residents. The insights and lessons learned from this project are intended to inform future initiatives and policy decisions aimed at creating a more sustainable and equitable food landscape in Utrecht.

Project Organization and Implementation

To organize this trial, Ineke Malsch took several key steps. In collaboration with the Eilandsteede city farm and Loos Utrecht cart stationed next to Bij Bosshardt, and with funding from the Initiatives Fund and the Catholic Caritas Utrecht, 10-euro vouchers were purchased. These vouchers were obtained from Eilandsteede city farm, Food for Good, and the Loos Utrecht cart.

The vouchers were distributed once a month on Fridays, starting from May 17, 2024, at Bij Bosshardt, located at Marco Pololaan 10, Kanaleneiland. The voucher giveaways took place on Friday mornings—May 17, June 14, July 12, August 2nd and September 2nd, 2024—from 10:00 AM to 12:00 PM. The visitors to the community center were a diverse group, including people from various backgrounds, such as Moroccan, Dutch, Turkish, and Surinamese communities. We have handed out a total of 186 vouchers from Loos and 34 vouchers from Utrecht Natuurlijk during the Trial.

Bij Bosshardt serves as a community center in the neighborhood, functioning as a social gathering place where people can sit, have tea, and talk to each other. It plays a crucial role in fostering community, allowing people to connect and learn about each other.

In addition to receiving a voucher, participants were given a leaflet/questionnaire containing important information about the project and a few questions about their experience.

Along with the physical questionnaire, participants were encouraged to provide their feedback during the next visit to Bij Bosshardt and engage in broader discussions about sustainable living and their current efforts towards it. This approach aimed to gather valuable insights and foster a sense of community involvement in sustainable practices.

The questionnaires distributed at Bij Bosshardt were translated into Dutch, English, Arabic and Dariya, to make it inclusive.

Systems Analysis

Europe requires a food system that is resilient and sustainable, benefiting both human health and ecosystems. To achieve this, it is essential to increase the production and consumption of organic food (*Lindgren et al., 2018*). Improving health outcomes for both people and the planet necessitates the inclusion of all socioeconomic and demographic groups in creating a more sustainable world (*King et al., 2021*). Unfortunately, current sustainable food systems often exclude underrepresented populations, typically involving only wealthy, well-educated individuals in sustainable practices (*Anantharaman et al., 2019*). Those from underrepresented groups frequently lack the means to become changemakers, which limits their participation in these initiatives.

In Utrecht, there is a noticeable disparity in health outcomes between different neighborhoods for example between neighborhoods such as Overvecht and Tuindorp, with a life expectancy difference of twelve years (*'The People in This Neighbourhood Live Longer, Healthier Lives,' 2021*). One significant factor contributing to this disparity is the affordability of healthy food. Statistics Netherlands (CBS) reports that last year, 36% of Dutch adults wanted to eat healthier, but one in six could not afford to do so (*Times, 2023*). Financial constraints severely limit household choices, often forcing people to opt for cheaper, less healthy options. In neighborhoods with limited access to affordable supermarkets, these constraints are even more pronounced.

By 2030, over 80% of the Dutch population will reside in urban areas (*Netherlands, 2018*). Therefore, addressing issues such as climate change, energy transition, and sustainable food chains is critical, with a particular focus on the health and well-being of urban residents.

The Red Cross has identified at least 450,000 adults in the Netherlands suffering from "hidden food shortages." These individuals often do not receive help due to ineligibility for food banks, shame, or lack of awareness about available aid options. Suzanne Segaar of the Red Cross highlights that many parents sacrifice their own meals for their children or substitute lemonade for a hot meal to save money, questioning how such situations persist in the Netherlands (*Times, 2024*).

To address food insecurity and promote healthier eating, many people turn to alternative food initiatives. These initiatives aim to support local food production, reduce food waste, promote fair trade, and advocate for food justice. While they offer innovative and promising solutions, their effectiveness can be limited by the funding and subsidies they receive. As a result, these initiatives often serve as short-term solutions rather than long-term answers to providing organic food sustainably.

In the Netherlands, systemic inequalities exacerbate challenges for marginalized groups, impacting their access to good jobs, education, and housing. Statistics show that only 7-14% of non-white individuals are in high-income groups, while 31-43% are in low-income groups (*Salverda et al., 2013*). The poorest neighborhoods, often populated by non-white residents, also have the highest numbers of food bank users. Factors like poverty and racial discrimination can reinforce each other, leading to higher obesity rates, which in turn create further barriers to employment and exacerbate both obesity and poverty (*Baciu et al., 2017*).

Sustainable and healthy food practices are predominantly adopted by well-educated and high-income individuals who can afford them. Socioeconomically disadvantaged individuals, despite being aware of healthier options, often prioritize cheap and convenient foods due to financial constraints *Pechey, R., & Monsivais, P. (2016)*. This misalignment between awareness and practice highlights the need for policies that address the specific needs of disadvantaged groups. Grassroots initiatives face challenges from top-down policies that do not consider local needs and from large corporations that may co-opt sustainable practices for profit (*Raj et al., 2022*).

To address and solve these complex issues, conducting a thorough system analysis is essential. This report has used helps identify interconnected elements and dynamics within the system, guiding more informed and strategic solutions.

At the local level, socioeconomically disadvantaged people face numerous hidden challenges in accessing healthy food. Grassroots initiatives, while deeply knowledgeable about local needs, often struggle to expand their reach and secure necessary support. At the municipal level, local food councils work to bridge the gap between grassroots efforts and higher-level policy making but face difficulties due to the absence of dedicated food policies and aldermen in some municipalities. At the policy level, fragmented approaches hinder the effective integration of food strategies. Local governments often set goals without clear pathways to achieve them, making it crucial to provide grassroots initiatives with channels to communicate their messages and include marginalized voices in policy discussions. Food councils can facilitate this communication, ensuring that the needs of affected individuals are addressed. By prioritizing inclusivity and supporting grassroots initiatives, policymakers can create strategies that are informed by the perspectives of those most affected, fostering sustainability and equity at the local level.

Systems thinking is usually applied in situations where we deal with complex wholes that comprise multiple entities, processes and interaction, which result in a range of outcomes which we may consider (*Cechvala, 2024*).

Our food system urgently needs a transformation, requiring a range of interventions that go even beyond the food value chain. There is no easy fix, however. We need an approach that includes all important players, including investors and governments. It should also include the food environment; all contextual factors that influence how consumers make choices. Only this way can we discover and leverage synergies and trade-offs to remedy the food system's malaise.

For the benefit of people and the planet, we must revitalize the food system.

Collaborations for the Trial

Loos Utrecht

Loos is a mobile zero-packaging supermarket operating in Utrecht. With a shop on wheels, Loos moves around the city, setting up at various spots to bring package-free groceries directly to the community. Customers can drop by at one of Loos's regular stops or arrange for the mobile shop to visit their location by appointment. Unlike a standard delivery service, Loos allows shoppers to visit together with their neighbors, fostering a sense of community.

The Loos vehicle is stocked with over 150 plant-based products, with a strong emphasis on organic and local items. Shoppers can choose how to take home their goods, making sustainable shopping convenient and accessible. Loos provides a practical way for everyone in Utrecht to shop for groceries without packaging, supporting both environmental sustainability and local producers.

<https://loosutrecht.nl/>

Eilandsteede city farm

Utrecht Natuurlijk manages five city farms and six city gardens, which are open year-round. One of these locations is Eilandsteede. These spaces allow residents to engage with animals, assist in gardening, and participate in educational activities at nature education centers. Their farm shops and catering establishments offer fresh, local produce and other goods.

They also have a history of school gardening, dating back to the 1930s. This initiative began to support families during tough times and continues today, helping primary school students grow and enjoy their own vegetables.

Their city gardens demonstrate how to grow local, eco-friendly food on a small scale, contributing to a greener and more diverse urban environment. They are committed to animal welfare, ensuring that animals live in clean, comfortable conditions with plenty of outdoor time and fresh food. Their "from source to plate" approach educates the community on responsible animal care and consumption. Through various projects, they work to strengthen nature and biodiversity in Utrecht, making the city greener, healthier, and more sustainable for everyone.

<https://www.utrechtnatuurlijk.nl/locaties/eilandsteede/>

Bij Bosshardt

Bij Bosshardt is a Community Living Room run by the Salvation Army in the Kanaleneiland neighborhood of Utrecht. It's a space created for the neighborhood and by the neighborhood. The center is open daily for various activities, and every morning from 10:00 to 12:00, people are welcome to drop in for a cup of coffee.

Community centers like Bij Bosshardt play a vital role in helping local residents bring their ideas and initiatives to life. It's more than just a place for social activities; it's also a place where people can find guidance and support when they need it. One of the key strengths of Bij Bosshardt is that it brings together people from different backgrounds, helping to build a stronger, more connected community.

<https://www.legerdesheils.nl/locatie/buurthuiskamerutrecht-2>

Initiative fund by Gemeente Utrecht:

Check the website: <https://www.utrecht.nl/bestuur-en-organisatie/initiatief-en-invloed/uw-initiatief/initiatievenfonds>

Results and Analysis:

The responses below were collected from the questionnaires and verbal feedback from participants during the action at Bij Bosshardt community center in Kanaleneiland. By analyzing these responses, we can better understand what the community needs and what can be done to support them in sustainable living.

These responses have been compared, and any similarities or contradictions have been noted in the comment section below each question. we have handed out a total of 186 vouchers from Loos and 34 vouchers from Utrecht Natuurlijk during the Trial

What did you buy with the voucher?

Voucher Action	May 17th	June 14th	July 12th	August 2nd	September 2nd
Vouchers Distributed	Loos Utrecht: 22 Vouchers Utrecht Natuurlijk: 9 vouchers	Loos Utrecht: 39 Vouchers Utrecht Natuurlijk: 9 vouchers	Loos Utrecht: 41 Vouchers Utrecht Natuurlijk: 16 vouchers	Loos Utrecht: 46 Vouchers Utrecht Natuurlijk: 0	Loos Utrecht: 38 vouchers Utrecht Natuurlijk: 0 vouchers
Answers summary	-Licorice / candies - Soup mix, pecans, nuts, chocolate -Tea, cinnamon, almonds, crunch nuts & seeds, cacao. nibs	-cashew nuts, licorice, cookies -Soap -Nuts without salt -unsalted nuts -cashew nuts, chocolate almonds -Nuts. -chia seeds, almonds, pistachios. -Walnuts -Walnuts -cashew nuts, licorice, cookies -muesli natural, rice, Sunflower Seeds. -muesli, nuts -cashew, walnuts -3 things kago and	-Figs -Cashew nuts, Mix nuts, almonds, hazelnuts, Brazil nuts -Coconut chips sprinkles, couscous -Cinnamon. almonds & coconut cubes with chocolate -Almond -Almond -Soap handmade -Pine kernel, Beans -Cashew nuts, almonds and chocolate almonds -Cashew nuts, mix nuts quinoa, muesli -Mixed nuts -Pistachios, hazelnuts	-Red rice -Almonds, mixed nuts, cashew nuts -Flaxseed, cashew nuts, black rice, granola, nuts, lentils -Chocolate almonds, Chocolate raspberries, pine nuts, coconut, granola chocolate and cinnamon almonds -Chocolate, raspberries, chocolate almonds, cinnamon almonds -Nuts -Peanuts -Basic muesli, oat flakes, chocolate oat flakes	-Brazil nuts, muesli -Walnuts, brown rice, cashew nuts -Walnuts -Walnuts -Brazil nuts -Pistachio +walnuts -Detergent, oil and Toothpaste -Nuts -Bulgur, quinoa, couscous -Muesli -Brazil nuts + Pistachio -Brazil nuts -Yellow split peas and walnuts -Cashew nuts/chocolate nuts

		hazelnut -2 - Chocolate -Mixed nuts, ginger in Chocolate and mango -Nuts -Salted cashew nuts -mixed nuts. -Rice, sprinkles, nuts -Rooibos tea + quinoa -pistachios, almonds, cashews -almond	-Whole grain penne unsalted cashew nuts herbal tea -Pecan nuts -Pecan nuts -Walnuts -Nuts -apple juice	-Almonds, tea, pistachio -Pistachio and almond -Pistachio and Brazil nuts -Brazil nuts -Pistachio and Brazil nuts -Walnuts -Nuts -Cashews -Pistachio and walnuts -Pistachio nuts -Pecan nuts	-Pistachio, mixed nuts -Nuts, ginger -Pistachio + mixed nuts -Pistachio + mixed nuts -Almonds and turmeric
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What do you think of the products you bought?

Voucher Action	May 17th	June 14th	July 12th	August 2nd	September 2nd
Answers summary	-Very nice products. Soup mixes good idea! -They are of excellent quality, very tasty and also good for the environment.	-very good for the skin -Very good -Delicious. -Delicious -good/tasty -Satisfied -of good quality -Excellent -they're good, Yummy -Muesli is very tasty. I still have to use rice. I use the sunflower seeds in baking. -Good. -very tasty -Delicious	-Tasty food -Delicious -Didn't like the square sprinkles (I prefer elongated) -Very, very tasty! Something I normally wouldn't choose but surprisingly Like -Perfectly healthy -Good -Very good -Very healthy -Good and tasty -Delicious! All look	-Healthy -Good -Delicious -Lovely, look good. -Good -Very tasty -Good -Good quality -Very nice / Nice -Delicious -Delicious -Delicious -Delicious -Excellent	-It looks very tasty. Tomorrow morning I am going to taste the muesli in my yogurt. -Amusing -Good -Good -Delicious -Delicious -I'm going to try them out, I don't know yet. -It's nice that there are organic products. -Good

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Delicious -Fresh and tasty, good combination -Delicious -Delicious -Delicious -Beautiful. -Looks good! -very good, tasty -I haven't tasted it yet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Good. -Looks good! -Good -Good -I think they are good products. -Tasty and they made cookies with it -Delicious -Excellent -Delicious -Apple juice was tasty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Delicious from Experience -Its good -Delicious -Delicious and lots -Good 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Delicious -Delicious -Good -A grade between 1-10: 7.5 -Perfect -Totally awesome -Delicious -Delicious -Delicious -Good
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Similarities and contradictions: The feedback collected through the questionnaire indicated a strong consensus that the quality of the organic food products was perceived as good and healthy by the participants

How did you find /what did you think of the store where you used the voucher?

Voucher Action	May 17th	June 14th	July 12th	August 2nd	September 2nd
Answers summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Community center - Accident -By fine coincidence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Terrific -Terrific. The Salvation Army is. allowed to -The trolley at the Salvation Army: very easy and lots of choice -small but mighty -amusing! -Satisfied -neat and a neat friendly gentleman 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Beautiful -Very nice and clear -Great service -Very nice! Nice system. Can even be dry in the rain. -Excellent -Excellent -Very good -Particularly good -Good and clear -Super fun and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Nice, good -Perfect -Super fun! Clear and a friendly man -Clear -Super fun and clear -Very nice -Excellent -Enjoyable -Nice people -Nice nut bar -Nice nut bar 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Nice, friendly and well-organized -Good -Good, nice -Amusing -Favorable -Favorable -Friendly employee, nice stuff -Nice, good planning -I missed flour -Nice: the cart

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -very nice and special -You will be helped in a friendly way -at the cart, very easy -Nice cart, lots of choice -Beautiful -Wonderful -Wonderful -I thought it was a well-kept mobile stall -Nice -at the Salvation Army -at the Salvation Army -Beautiful -Super nice shop, clear & you can see that these are organic products. -neat, nice man -good 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear. -Nice, uncluttered, Cute. -Good -Good -With the cart, a wide range. -Good -Good -Good -Fun and special -Very useful -Great service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Nice nut bar -Amusing -Bij Bosshardt, nice Surroundings -Good -Good -Very handy -A nice invention: the nut cart -Amusing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Amusing -The nut bar is nice -Good idea -Nice people, good Products -Good -Plenty of choices -Perfect, very happy with it -Perfect, nice that this is possible! -Could be a bit more extensive
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Similarities and contradictions: The responses clearly indicated that people were more willing to obtain the voucher from the Loos Utrecht, conveniently located right outside Bij Bosshardt. This accessibility made it easy for them to get organic food, highlighting that convenience is a top priority when it comes to eating organic food.

Do you want to buy organic or sustainable products more often? What do you need for this?

Voucher Action	May 17th	June 14th	July 12th	August 2nd	September 2nd
Answers summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Yes, support -Yes, more money -Yes, I would really like to. A bigger amount to spend. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Sure -Sure -Yes. More points where you can buy it -Yes, a larger budget 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Maybe tomorrow. bought 1st time. -I'm getting older. Perhaps with a discount. -Not too expensive, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Vegetables and meat -Yes. More Stores -Yes, definitely. That it becomes more affordable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Yes. A little more time to go to the green store. -Yes. A shop on Kanaleneiland. -I don't know

		<p>-yes maybe -yes please, not too expensive (cheap) -for my health -Yes definitely, but very pricey and little Supply -yes. More shops. -I buy organic products in the supermarket when I get the chance, such as dairy, flour -Yes, more offers in the area. -It depends on the price! -yes, like to eat and healthy. -yes, like to eat and healthy. -may, not necessary -I want to do it much more often -yes, just not enough budget. -yes, but it doesn't work in terms of budget -Money, The Shop -Yes, there may be more of these mobile shops! -Yes, if it's cheaper. -Nuts</p>	<p>nearby -In this way, I would love to. Handy without plastic too. -Honey -Honey -Stimulate -Preferably with a discount -Yes, more often these kinds of mobile shops -Yes. Even more coupons! -Yes, definitely! I would like to eat healthier, but it is often unaffordable for me. It would be nice if it became more accessible. -Yes, visit more often -Yes. -Yes, I choose what is affordable for me. -Sometimes money is an issue -Sometimes more money -If there's a store, definitely -Fruit and vegetables -Not too expensive, nearby</p>	<p>-Yes, these vouchers -Yes, these vouchers! -No, organic is too expensive -Not familiar with the product. -Yes, I buy organic products in the supermarket, I am selective about that. -Certainly, more salary -Yes, sometimes. -Yes, sometimes. -Sometimes -Yes, I already buy them, sometimes -Yes -Maybe so -Yes, it doesn't cut short -I can just do that -More income</p>	<p>-More budget -Yes -Yes -Yes, please, that they become a little cheaper -No, not normally. Too expensive, but healthy. -Yes, I'm on a low budget, so I can't do it all the time -More offer -Yes, but then I have to have enough money -I've been doing that sometimes -I buy all kinds of things, because I use it. -Good Finances/Income -Yes, offers -The days and where it is -Yes. No money. Too little to buy that. -Yes, but little budget due to benefits -I don't buy organic food often; it is a bit expensive. I can't afford the extra things you need. -More points of sale</p>
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Similarities and contradictions: The responses revealed that while many people are interested in buying organic food, budget constraints are a significant barrier. Those who do purchase organic products often do so for health reasons, though only a few can afford them regularly. There is a desire among some respondents for more organic shops and greater convenience, but affordability remains the top concern. Many appreciated the voucher program and expressed a wish for it to continue, as it allowed them to access healthier options within their limited budgets.

What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?

Voucher Action	May 17th	June 14th	July 12th	August 2nd	September 2nd
Answers summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Continue -Food bank -More offers on organic products or vouchers to spend on organic products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Offer more and small packages -U-pas budget expansion via the U-pas -sponsoring the store so that I can buy the groceries cheaper -to accommodate something -More supply and larger supply -Cooperate with this -An allowance for people with a low income would be desirable, healthy food leads to health and saves on illness and other costs. -more supply. -a lot of people stand at markets or shopping malls. -more money -More budget -Opening the budget -I already buy organic -Bid in Kanaleneiland 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Branding. Inquire through community Centers. -Make it more common more in the regular stores? Using subsidies to make it cheaper. -Things like this, or a discount with U-pas. -Helping for poor people -Low price -An allowance per ID -Offering more alternatives like this -At various places in the district. -Standing in different places and supporting the residents financially. -Making it attractive -Support. -I don't know! -Opening Stores Or organic products may be involved in u- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Low price -What's good for you is good for us. -Give vouchers. -Handing out vouchers -Handing out vouchers -The price should be low -Don't know -Financially supporting, healthy products lead to health and reduce healthcare costs -Discounts, etc. -I don't know -I don't know -I don't know -I don't know -Mobile shop -Often, it's too expensive -I bought organic pointed cabbage. -More frequent receipts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Spread the word -Reduce VAT, increase income -Making it more accessible (e.g. in neighborhoods such as Kanaleneiland) -Occasionally in AH and supermarket -Affordable through offers, e.g. -Make it better known, more stores -Something like that, where I can buy organic products with a voucher -I don't know -Sell cheaper -Food bank for organic products -Opening a store -More places -Giving more budget -More offer

		on the market! -making it cheaper by means of sponsoring -cheaper.	pas card. -Make it more common more in the regular stores? Using subsidies to make it cheaper		
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Similarities and contradictions: One of the most frequently mentioned ideas was to continue the voucher initiative, although not necessarily as a direct copy. Participants suggested that regular stores could offer similar vouchers for organic food, making them more widely available and extending the initiative to other neighborhoods.

Another common suggestion was to enable the use of the U-pas (a discount card for low-income residents) for purchasing organic food. Currently, this isn't an option, but many participants felt that allowing U-pas credits to be spent on organic food would be a more effective use of the card.

The third most popular suggestion was to make organic food more affordable. Some participants weren't sure what to suggest, but a few thought it should be more convenient to buy organic food, such as by having organic food stands in every neighborhood.

Do you have any other tips for us?

Voucher Action	May 17th	June 14th	July 12th	August 2nd	September 2nd
Answers summary	-No -Let us help with the vegetable garden as a volunteer -No, except that it's a super action that I'm very grateful for.	-50/50 -stamp save and after 4x divide data voucher you can buy for 50% to 60%. You only pay a small amount. -Given the short time that the cart has been present, maybe an extra seller -No, not now. -No. -No. -entry in municipal	-No thank you! I am very happy with it. -Don't think only for the rich -Thinking for poor people - ID then you get 1 Voucher -Coming to get everything without sacrificing any contribution and insisting at the (cart) store that the	-With u-pas low price -Do this more often. -No -No -Think of poor people -Not really -Putting up posters in neighborhoods -No -No -No -No -No, not really	-Make it cheaper, and I must eat more seasonally myself. -No. -Not really. -Nuts are not such a success, I prefer to buy them packaged. -No. -No. -More stalls -no

		<p>Directories.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -No, it looked clear and neat. Good luck. -Keep going -Discount vouchers can be given -think it's a good start -It would be nice to be at the market with a mobile shop, Friday. Super fun! A better environment starts with you! -Multiple products 	<p>salesperson must hurry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -More organic -More organic. Connecting farmers and residents. -Not now. -This is well taken care of 	-No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -No, that's fine. -Keep up the good work -No. -I am glad that this alternative exists.
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Similarities and contradictions: A few participants shared additional tips, though most felt that the current initiative is a good start and should be continued. Some mentioned that discount vouchers could be beneficial in the future. One standout idea was to encourage people to volunteer at local farms in exchange for organic food. Another suggestion was to make mobile shops more common, increasing accessibility to organic products. Additionally, the idea of allowing U-pas holders to use their credits for organic food was also highlighted as a potential improvement.

Verbal reactions

Voucher Action	May 17th	June 14th	July 12th	August 2nd	September 2nd
Answers summary	<p>Packaging-Free Products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Loos Utrecht sells products without packaging, requiring customers to bring their own. - Nostalgic comparison to old practices of 	<p>Product Experience and Feedback</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Muesli was tasty, but brown rice required a long cooking time. - Positive feedback on the appearance of the cart and products available. 	<p>U-pas Usage and Accessibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inquiry if U-pas can be used to buy organic food. - Current activities for U-pas holders require a subscription. - Suggestion for U-pas 	<p>U-pas Concerns A person disapproves the automatic renewal of U-pas-credit and wants to spend the remaining credit on organic food or other useful items.</p> <p>Organic Food</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Stores like Lidl, Dirk, Aldi, and Jumbo offer a variety of organic products, though items like organic meat and coffee availability vary. Organic food can be expensive, limiting access for low-income

	<p>reusable packaging. - Query on why virgin plastic is used instead of recycled plastic. - Lidl offers packaging-free fruit and vegetables, but not other stores. General positive sentiment about packaging-free shopping being a smart and special idea.</p> <p>Product Purchases and Usage - Purchases included liquor ice, candy, muesli, sunflower seeds, brown rice, raspberries with chocolate, soup mix, pistachios, cashew nuts, and cumin. - Usage of products: brown rice used daily, sunflower seeds added to muesli, cumin used on eggs. -Some items were bought as special treats due to high costs.</p> <p>Positive Feedback on Products -Satisfaction with the quality of products such as soup mix, pistachios, and cumin. -Happiness with purchases enhances</p>	<p>- Popularity of walnuts and muesli noted. - Absence of tea on the cart, but availability at Food4good. - Availability of natural licorice on the cart.</p> <p>Shopping and Availability - Lack of organic food shops in Kanaleneiland, with the nearest being Eko plaza on the Amsterdamse straatweg. - Organic products available at large supermarkets but limited in variety.</p> <p>Personal and Historical Context - Personal anecdotes of growing up with fresh, homegrown produce and high-quality food. - Comparison of past food quality to current supermarket offerings, with a preference for traditional methods and fresh produce.</p> <p>Volunteer Activities and Discounts - Discount received at Food4good for volunteering.</p>	<p>to be usable at electronics and white goods stores, fast food outlets, and for discounts on day trips.</p> <p>Positive Feedback on Organic Product - Children enjoyed the nuts bought through the coupon campaign. - Positive feedback on the quality of products like blueberry juice, herbal tea, and nuts, despite their high cost.</p> <p>Affordability Concerns - Difficulty affording organic products regularly due to high prices. - Specific mention of the high cost of nuts and the inability to purchase them frequently. - Concern over the high cost of insurance despite municipal discounts.</p> <p>Health Benefits - Nuts and muesli help with iron deficiency and digestive health.</p> <p>General Suggestions - Conducting a trial with subsidized organic groceries at community center De Nieuwe Jutter.</p>	<p>Initiative Loos Utrecht is open to collaborating if U-pas tests an organic food option.</p> <p>Kanaleneiland Gardens The Alexander Garden is a neighborhood garden for children. Residents can have their own small plots.</p> <p>Green Initiatives Four projects in Kanaleneiland include public gardens, a children’s food forest, and vertical gardens (buurtnatuur030.nl).</p> <p>Gardening Efforts A lady has a garden in Nieuwegein. Organic mint is grown at Bij Bosshardt, with potential for more gardening.</p> <p>Voucher Use A man was advised to use Utrecht Natuurlijk vouchers at the Petting Zoo in Transwijk Park.</p> <p>Need for a Social Map There’s no comprehensive</p>	<p>individuals.</p> <p>-Visiting Bij Bosshardt for coffee allows people to meet others, enhancing community connections.</p> <p>-A market cart visits Kanaleneiland on Fridays, but the owner can only stay if there are enough customers. They need permission from the ward board to operate regularly. -Younger generations are more conscious of organic food, though affordability remains a challenge.</p> <p>-Healthy foods like pistachios are expensive, making cheaper alternatives like peanuts more accessible for low-income people.</p> <p>-Organic food at the market stall caters to diverse cultures and religions, with a wide range of dietary options.</p> <p>-Eilandsteede is appreciated for offering delicious organic apple juice and a pleasant</p>
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	<p>daily experiences.</p> <p>Affordability and Economic Concerns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty affording products like pecans and other high-cost items. - Mention of limited funds from welfare and high prices at stores like Albert Heijn. - High cost of cumin in local shops compared to purchasing it in bulk from Morocco. <p>Community and Volunteer Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Participation in community activities such as helping at a bird sanctuary and working in a vegetable garden. -Volunteers receive free vegetables and appreciation for their work. <p>Miscellaneous Reactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Interest in saving up for mini wharf soaps. -Deliberation over which types of nuts to purchase. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Volunteering experiences shared, such as at Buurtbuik in Sterrenzicht and Nieuwe Jutter. <p>Affordability Concerns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organic nuts being expensive and not affordable regularly. - Desire for affordable, high-quality food like past experiences. <p>Suggestions and Tips</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suggestion to allocate the remaining €45 on the U-pas to organic products instead of limiting it to the OV-chipkaart. - Mention of honey varieties at Lidl and tips on distinguishing natural honey from sugar-based alternatives. - Positive reception of the voucher as a gift and its potential to surprise and delight family members. <p>General Impressions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Satisfaction with the quality of the products from the cart. - Appreciation for the voucher and its benefits, such as buying nuts for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allowing U-pas to be used at more hairdressers. - Addressing adolescent needs for fitting in with friends through affordable clothing options. <p>Specific Product Feedback</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive feedback on pecans being crispy. - Issues with pistachios not being crispy. - Inquiry about the availability of honey at Eilandsteede. <p>Economic Concerns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High taxes on benefits causing financial strain. - Mention of inflation impacting purchasing power. 	<p>overview of social justice or green space organizations in Kanaleneiland. An online map is suggested, but communication remains challenging.</p>	<p>environment through its voucher program.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Organic cashews went stale quickly; it's better to buy packaged. Cooking time for products like brown rice can be challenging for busy schedules. -A participant shared their experience using techniques like hay boxes to cook rice and beans. They prefer organic short-boiled rice for convenience. -Organic flour is hard to find at the market stall. Some participants enjoy baking their own sourdough bread at home, though it takes time and effort. -There's interest in offering sourdough bread-making lessons and cooking workshops, particularly in organic recipes like quinoa and bulgur. -Participants are interested in group cooking sessions to try new recipes and learn
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		family visits.			more about healthy, organic food preparation.
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Similarities and contradictions: The most common points that emerged were a strong interest in packaging-free and organic shopping, with participants expressing positive sentiments toward initiatives like Loos Utrecht and a desire for more stores to adopt similar practices. However, affordability was a significant concern, with many finding it difficult to afford organic products, particularly nuts, due to high prices. There was also strong interest in expanding the use of U-pas' credits to purchase organic food. Participants appreciated the quality of the organic products they could access, though some items were seen as special treats due to their cost. Additionally, suggestions included expanding organic food access through mobile shops, subsidized grocery trials, and community gardens, as well as allowing people to volunteer at local farms in exchange for organic produce.

The feedback gathered through questionnaires and conversations at Bij Bosshardt reveals a strong interest in living sustainably. However, various obstacles are hindering the adoption of organic or healthier food options in participants' daily lives, which will be discussed in more detail later.

Important aspects of the trial

1. It is crucial to recognize that the participants at Bij Bosshardt come from diverse cultural backgrounds, including Moroccan, Turkish, Syrian, Surinamese, and Arabic communities. These cultural differences significantly influence their opinions and suggestions, often shaped by their own cultural contexts and experiences. Understanding these nuances is essential to creating a more inclusive environment where everyone's needs and preferences are considered. Although navigating these cultural differences may be complex, it is a critical step toward fostering more equitable and just living conditions. This ensures that solutions are not only effective but also respectful of the diverse perspectives within the community.
2. A significant gap in the responses was the lack of feedback from younger people. Since the attendees were primarily elderly, the insights gathered were limited to this specific age group and their perspectives. Unlike younger individuals, who tend to be more opinionated and in tune with current trends, the elderly participants often expressed uncertainty, frequently responding with "I don't know" or "I'm not sure." This suggests that they may not be fully aware of certain aspects of the topics discussed. As a

result, the absence of younger voices in the trial led to an incomplete understanding of the broader community's views on organic food.

3. Holding the voucher actions on a Friday once a month was effective, but the last session, which took place on a Monday, provided valuable insights. Unlike the previous sessions, where we often heard the same perspectives and advice, the Monday session brought in fresh viewpoints. This suggests that changing the day of the week can attract different participants and foster a more diverse range of perspectives. To ensure broader participation and avoid repetition, varying the timing of these sessions is key to gathering more comprehensive feedback.

Several recurring themes emerged from the conversations, including concerns about affordability, convenience, and awareness, as well as the scarcity of organic food shops. Other notable points included the lack of appeal in organic food stores, the inability to use Upas credits to purchase organic food, the challenge of buying organic food for an entire family, the absence of discounts or vouchers at organic stores, the preference for sticking to established routines, and the lack of culturally appropriate food options in organic stores.

These insights underscore the need to address these barriers to make organic and healthy food more accessible and appealing to a broader audience.

Obstacles as discussed by the participants:

Affordability

Affordability emerged as the most common concern among participants in the voucher program. Research indicates that in the Netherlands, sustainable food practices are adopted by white, well-educated, and high-income individuals, often referred to as the "green elite" (Brons, n.d.). In contrast, those attending community centers like Bij Bosshardt often come from culturally diverse backgrounds and face different socioeconomic challenges.

Many participants expressed a desire to eat healthily but are constrained by the cost, leading them to opt for the cheapest available options. Organic food is perceived as unaffordable, not just for consumers but also for farmers, due to the higher costs associated with organic farming compared to conventional methods. This economic barrier makes it difficult for people to make the switch to organic products.

While reducing prices is a complex and long-term challenge, it is crucial to explore immediate, practical solutions. Initiatives like this voucher program offer valuable insights into how we can begin addressing these affordability issues. By testing and refining such programs, we can identify strategies that make healthy, sustainable food more accessible without waiting for broader systemic changes. This might not be the best path to take but conducting trials like this gives us the authentic perspective of the people who are struggling from the affordability factor of the food the most.

Manual for a trial of subsidized organic groceries

To support residents with limited budgets in accessing affordable organic groceries, “Duurzaam Utrecht 2030” has developed a manual to guide neighborhoods and organizations through a trial program offering subsidized organic food. The manual is designed to help others organize similar initiatives within their communities. This manual is a result of trials conducted in Lunetten and Kanaleneiland, where “Duurzaam Utrecht 2030” collaborated with local organizations, community centers, and citizens to understand the barriers to accessing organic food. The goal in publishing this manual is to provide a resource for organizations and communities interested in promoting sustainable living.

The detailed guidelines of the manual are provided in the Annexure.

Convenience

Another recurring theme was the importance of convenience. When given the option between Loos Utrecht and the Eilandsteede city farm, all participants chose Loos Utrecht, which is located right outside the community center at Bij Bosshardt. This choice highlighted why many participants might not choose organic stores—they are often located far from residential areas, making it inconvenient for people to travel long distances just to buy organic food.

Additionally, participants frequently mentioned that supermarkets should offer discounts on organic food. This would make it easier for them to afford organic options and eliminate the need to make a separate trip to an organic store. Loos Utrecht was particularly attractive to many participants because it reminded them of similar market carts in their home countries, making it easy and familiar to buy food.

The convenience factor suggests that community centers in different neighborhoods could be ideal locations for placing organic stores or carts like Loos Utrecht. Even without discounts, having these options nearby could be a starting point for introducing people to organic food. Participants' responses made it clear that convenience plays a crucial role in influencing their food choices. By consistently

exposing people to organic stores or carts, we might spark curiosity and gradually encourage a shift toward more sustainable food practices.

Awareness

Throughout the trial, it became evident that many participants lacked awareness of what organic food is and how it differs from conventional options, highlighting a significant gap in education about healthy eating. This gap is critical and suggests that more effort needs to be directed toward educating people about healthy food choices. Without proper awareness and education, some participants were unsure about the changes they should make to incorporate more organic food into their diets, revealing a fundamental misunderstanding of what organic food entails.

This observation raises several important questions: Why are these individuals unaware of organic or healthy food? What does their current diet consist of? How do they define healthy food within their cultural context? Does their culture have a different understanding of what is considered healthy?

These questions open new avenues for inquiry and point to the need for a more targeted educational approach. Understanding their dietary habits and cultural perceptions of health is crucial for developing effective educational programs. By addressing these gaps, we can better inform and empower individuals to make healthier food choices that align with their cultural practices and improve their overall well-being. It is also important to note that what might be considered healthy in one culture is not considered healthy in another culture.

Scarcity of organic food shops

Scarcity of organic food shops emerged as another significant theme during the trial. Many participants pointed out that there are no organic stores in their neighborhoods, making it difficult for them to purchase organic food even if they want to. This lack of accessibility highlights a broader issue: organic food stores are often concentrated in affluent areas, where residents are more likely to afford them. While the concept of organic farming is not new, the availability of organic products has typically been limited to certain areas, often excluding lower-income neighborhoods.

Moreover, many organic farms are located outside urban centers, adding to the difficulty of accessing organic products. The cost and inconvenience of traveling to these locations, combined with the already high prices of organic food, create significant barriers for people who might otherwise be interested in making healthier choices.

In this context, initiatives like Loos Utrecht <https://loosutrecht.nl/> can play a crucial role. By bringing organic produce directly to different neighborhoods, especially those underserved by traditional organic stores, Loos can make organic food more accessible and convenient. This approach not only reduces the travel burden but also introduces organic options to communities that may not have previously had access.

In Utrecht, initiatives like Rechtstreex <https://www.rechtstreex.nl/> and VOKO <https://vokoutrecht.nl/> offer convenient ways to order organic, locally-sourced food online and pick it up at neighborhood locations. Rechtstreex, for example, lets customers order fresh, regional products from local farms and collect them from designated points. They are actively expanding in Utrecht, though currently Kanaleneiland is not listed as one of their locations.

VOKO Utrecht operates through a member-based, non-profit model where participants can order organic groceries every two weeks. Members pick up their orders at Café Averechts in Utrecht's city center.

Organizations often struggle to expand to different neighborhoods due to a lack of resources, such as funding for infrastructure, equipment, and staff. Financial constraints can limit their ability to invest in necessary facilities or hire additional personnel. Additionally, space limitations, particularly for things like refrigeration or storage, can hinder growth, as seen in city farms like Utrecht Natuurlijk <https://www.utrechtnatuurlijk.nl/> which lack the facilities to support larger-scale food distribution. Expanding operations also requires specialized technology and logistics systems, which may not be feasible without external support or funding. As a result, growth can be difficult without adequate financial backing, space, and operational capacity.

Solutions and Suggestions

The most common solutions and suggestions shared by the participants are discussed below, along with the proposed action plan moving forward.

Expand and Continue the Voucher Program

Continuing the voucher program for organic food is suggested by a lot of participants, as price remains the main concern for participants living below the poverty line. However, financial constraints at the municipal level, as highlighted by the Mayor of Utrecht, pose

significant challenges. While the importance of providing healthy and sustainable food options to all residents is recognized, limited resources prevent the municipality from funding every initiative, including a food voucher program, which would cost over €11 million annually (The letter from the Mayor is attached in the Annex) To address this, engaging local business associations, particularly those focused on organic and sustainable products, could lead to partnerships that offer bonus cards for organic items, potentially financed through their Entrepreneurs' Fund. Expanding sustainable activities in community centers, in collaboration with organizations like Duurzaam Utrecht 2030, could also raise awareness and accessibility to healthy food options, with potential funding from the Initiatives Fund. Additionally, the fragmented policy approach to food, which currently spans climate, circular economy, and health domains, needs a more integrated strategy, which the municipality is exploring. Given the financial constraints at the municipal level, securing funding from national or European Union sources could be a viable alternative, but a detailed action plan is essential to move forward.

“Duurzaam Utrecht 2030” is organizing a new project in St. Maarten, where for every product someone buys, another product is donated <https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/en-gb/bioboodschappen>. This initiative is a collaboration with students from Grafisch Lyceum Utrecht, Moestuin Maarschalkerweerd, Utrecht Natuurlijk, and the Voedselbank Utrecht (Food Bank). The idea is to make healthy, organic food more accessible to everyone, especially those who are struggling financially. This project is a follow-up to a recommendation from Elizabete Fedcenko's report about a trial in the Lunetten last year.

Another project which is Cultivate <https://cultivate-project.eu/> is an EU-funded initiative aimed at promoting Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) to create sustainable, inclusive, and resilient urban food systems. It will develop the Food Sharing Compass, a platform with tools to support FSIs, policymakers, and citizens.

The Municipality of Utrecht is central to this effort, aligning with its ‘Healthy Urban Living’ strategy, which prioritizes health in urban development. Utrecht ranked first in the 2022 EU Regional Competitiveness Index. The municipality is also leading the Rijnvliet, Edible Neighborhood project, transforming public spaces into edible green areas and a food forest through collaboration with residents. <https://cultivate-project.eu/cities/utrecht/>

Increase Accessibility to Organic Products through Mobile Shops

Participants also expressed concerns about the limited availability of organic stores, making it difficult for them to find or reach these stores conveniently. To address this, introducing organic shops in neighborhoods could be an effective solution. These shops would not only make organic products more accessible but also raise awareness among residents who may not be familiar with organic food. However, opening new food stores in the Netherlands involves navigating Dutch business law, which includes understanding the legal structure, taxation laws, and employment regulations. These factors significantly impact daily operations and financial responsibilities, as well as the registration and permitting process. Collaborating with already established businesses might be a more practical and efficient approach. For example, neighborhoods like Lunetten and Kanaleneiland in Utrecht could partner with mobile shops like Loos Utrecht to bring to community centers on specific days. However, buying from organic shops can still be quite expensive, so it would be beneficial to introduce discount vouchers specifically for these visits.

U-pass for Organic groceries

The U-pas is a valuable resource for low-income individuals and families in Utrecht, providing free access to a variety of sports and cultural activities, discounts on products, and reduced prices at tourist attractions. It also includes special contributions to ensure that children can participate in enriching experiences, regardless of their family's financial situation.

A few of the participants suggested expanding the U-pas program to allow a portion of its budget to be used for purchasing organic groceries. Currently, U-pas' holders cannot use their benefits for organic food, despite a strong interest in these healthier options. By partnering with organic stores, this proposal seeks to reduce the financial barriers that prevent low-income residents from accessing organic food. This collaboration would enable U-pas' holders to use their benefits at participating organic stores, making healthy and sustainable food choices more accessible.

However, according to the U-pas administration, there is an existing agreement that the U-pass should not be used for consumable goods. Despite this restriction, organizations running similar initiatives can offer discounts to U-pass holders. It's important to note that these discounts would not be reimbursed by the U-pas program or the municipality; the organization itself would bear the cost as a contribution to the community.

For organizations interested in engaging with low-income residents and encouraging healthy food choices, it is recommended to contact the municipality directly. The U-pas administration suggests this because they work on behalf of the municipality and may not always have the most up-to-date understanding of the broader initiatives related to healthy food access.

Involving city farms for volunteering and providing healthy/organic food

Another suggestion was promoting access to organic and healthy food in Utrecht is to create a volunteer program where people can work on city farms in exchange for fresh produce. By helping with daily farm tasks, volunteers would get hands-on experience in sustainable farming and, in return, receive a share of the farm's harvest. This means they would get to take home a variety of fresh fruits, vegetables, and herbal foods that might otherwise be too expensive for them. This would be helpful for low-income families, allowing them to eat healthier without spending extra money. It also supports the city's commitment to sustainability by encouraging environmentally friendly farming practices and reducing the distance food must travel. Plus, it helps people feel more connected to their food and the community.

This volunteer program could offer many benefits. Volunteers could learn useful skills in sustainable farming, gain a better understanding of where their food comes from, and enjoy the health benefits of eating fresh, organic produce. It would also create a sense of community and shared purpose as volunteers work together on these farms.

However, the challenge lies in establishing effective collaboration with city farms. Registered, for-profit farms may not be able to accommodate volunteers, so it is essential to focus on non-profit farms that are more likely to participate. Even among non-profit farms, only a limited number may be open to such arrangements. Therefore, identifying and engaging with these farms is crucial to making the program a reality.

Growing Organic Food at Home and in the Community

Another key insight from the voucher session was the potential for individuals to use their own gardens as alternatives to supermarkets for accessing organic food. Growing organic produce at home not only makes fresh, healthy food more accessible but also encourages a more active lifestyle. Additionally, with the abundance of online resources, learning how to start and maintain an organic garden has become easier than ever.

Furthermore, the option of utilizing community center gardens was also explored. This provides an opportunity for those without private garden space to engage in gardening, fostering a sense of community while promoting sustainability. Both approaches empower individuals to take control of their food sources, stay active, and connect with others.

Supermarket Impact

Research was conducted to analyze the prices of common products in major Dutch supermarkets with the goal of finding the most cost-effective ways to purchase organic products. The findings were quite revealing. The cost of organic products can vary significantly depending on the supermarket you choose. Interestingly, some organic items at discount stores such as Lidl or Aldi can be less expensive than non-organic alternatives at pricier supermarkets like Albert Heijn or Jumbo (*Fieke, 2023*). This price discrepancy means that if you usually shop at higher-end stores, it's worth considering a shift to discount supermarkets to find more affordable organic options. Additionally, organic own-brand products often come at a lower price compared to premium non-organic brands, further emphasizing the potential savings. Exploring different stores and prioritizing budget-friendly organic choices can help you integrate organic products into your diet without overspending.

Cost-Effective Organic Choices

When looking for budget-friendly organic options, it's useful to know which products offer the best value. Many organic items are only slightly more expensive than their non-organic counterparts, typically less than €0.25 or 25% more. For instance, organic canned chickpeas, canned tomatoes, pasta (penne), peanut butter, and bananas are relatively inexpensive and can help you include organic options in your shopping without straining your budget. Conversely, some products like parmesan cheese, salted peanuts, basmati rice, frozen green beans, and cherry tomatoes have a more significant price difference between organic and non-organic versions. To make the most of your budget, prioritize buying organic items with smaller price differences and consider sticking to non-organic for products with higher price disparities. This approach helps you enjoy organic foods while keeping costs in check.

Cooking Together (Cookbook)

A "Cooking Together" event could be a great way to bring the community together for a shared meal while promoting healthy eating. It would allow people to socialize, learn how to prepare nutritious recipes, and make healthy food more accessible, especially for those who may not know how to cook for themselves. A cookbook with simple, healthy recipes could be provided to make it easier for participants to continue cooking healthy meals at home. This event could also foster stronger social connections and create a more supportive, health-conscious community.

Two initiatives that bring people together through cooking:

Lunetten**Cookbook****Project:**

The Lunetten Cookbook Project started by “Duurzaam Utrecht 2030” after conversations with visitors of the Giveaway Shop in Lunetten, where people shared the idea of creating a cookbook. The project will collect sustainable, healthy, and affordable recipes from local residents. Together, they will try out these recipes, then share a photo, the recipe, and a story about why it's a favorite. <https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/en-gb/kookboek-lunetten>

Milouda's**Cooking****Group****in****Kanaleneiland:**

Milouda's Cooking Group is an initiative in Kanaleneiland where people gather to cook and share traditional Moroccan dishes, including Milouda's famous couscous. It helps build community through food. [Stadsdiner Utrecht](#).

Urban Farming: Growing Your Own Food on Place Roofs

Encourage residents and businesses to utilize rooftop spaces for growing organic food. This solution promotes self-sufficiency and reduces the need for imported produce. Rooftop gardens can be shared spaces or managed by individual households, offering a way to grow fruits, vegetables, and herbs. Integrating green roofs into the urban infrastructure also helps with insulation, reduces air pollution, and improves biodiversity. Community workshops can teach people how to maintain these gardens and grow food organically in limited spaces.

Affordable Neighborhood Restaurant

Opening an organic restaurant in the neighborhood that serves fresh, affordable meals to the community is key. A great example is *Volkskantine* <https://mensa-mensa.nl/de-missie/> in Rotterdam Zuid, where people can have nutritious meals at snack bar prices. Residents can also cook a healthy weekly menu together under the guidance of a chef, and children can participate in free weekly cooking classes. The restaurant could source ingredients from local farmers, rooftop gardens, or school gardens. To keep prices low, the restaurant could be a cooperative venture, run by community members, and offer pay-what-you-can options or meal-sharing programs. Additionally, this space could act as a community hub, offering cooking classes, food preservation workshops, and communal dinners.

School Gardens

School gardens, where children can actively participate in growing food and learning about sustainability, nutrition, and ecology. These gardens could supply fresh produce for school cafeterias, giving students access to organic, healthy meals while teaching them valuable

life skills. Additionally, kids can be involved in meal preparation at school, fostering a sense of responsibility for their food and health. Educational programs can integrate gardening into science, biology, and environmental studies.

The concept of school gardens, where children actively participate in growing food, aligns with initiatives like **Alexandertuin** <https://www.buurtnatuur030.nl/> in Utrecht, a local urban farm that engages children with gardening and sustainability. Additionally, **Utrecht Natuurlijk** <https://www.utrechtnatuurlijk.nl/> offers educational programs for schools, including gardening lessons that integrate into broader environmental and science curricula. These gardens provide fresh produce that can be used in school cafeterias, teaching students about nutrition and ecology.

VAT on Fruits & Vegetables

Lobbying for the reduction or elimination of VAT on organic fruits and vegetables will make healthy food more affordable for everyone. A 0% VAT policy on organic produce encourages more people to choose these options and supports local farmers who prioritize sustainable agricultural practices. This measure would help bring down costs for low-income families, ensuring better access to fresh, nutritious food without financial strain.

Feedback on Trial Conclusions and Recommendations

On September 13th, at Bij Bosshardt in Kanaleneiland, the results of the organic food trial were presented to participants. A flyer was distributed, summarizing the trial's purpose, methodology, and outcomes. Thirteen participants offered a variety of suggestions, which are categorized and summarized below:

1. Loos Utrecht Cart Availability and U-pas Partnership

Cart Frequency and Location:

There is a request for the Loos Utrecht cart to visit Kanaleneiland more frequently. Loos Utrecht allows customers to book appointments with the cart, visiting various locations across the city. Customers can schedule visits through their website, selecting convenient times and locations. They announce upcoming visits the day before, offering flexibility. To improve accessibility, it's suggested that Loos Utrecht increases visits to Kanaleneiland, possibly at the shopping center market, and uses platforms like the 'Samen Kanaleneiland' app or social media for advance announcements to attract more visitors. Visit [Loos Utrecht - Maak een afspraak](#) for more details.

U-pas Discount

There is interest in having Loos Utrecht become a partner of U-pas to provide a discount for U-pas holders. Participants with experience in discounted meals for U-pas' holders (e.g., at Resto van Harte) indicated that such initiatives work well, but not all dining tables offering discounts are listed as official U-pas' partners. <https://www.u-pas.nl/> On the website people can find the organizations offering discounts.

2. Food for Good and Volunteering Opportunities

Volunteer Experience

One participant shared their positive experience volunteering at Food for Good, which is located in Transwijk Park. While anyone can volunteer, the participant noted that they haven't seen volunteers with physical disabilities involved. The volunteers get a discount on the fresh, unsprayed produce available at the small shop, where they can pick flowers or purchase tea, vegetables, and handmade items.

Events

Food for Good is actively organizing community events, such as the Harvest Festival on September 22 at Eilandsteede. It is important to make these initiatives more widely known within the community.

3. Community Gardens and Skepticism About Participation

Alexanderhof Vegetable Garden:

All spaces in the Alexanderhof children's vegetable garden are occupied, with children from the neighborhood growing a variety of plants such as potatoes, sunflowers, and tomatoes.

Other Community Gardens:

Community centers like De Paraplu and Bij Bosshardt also have gardens. While De Paraplu sometimes sells surplus produce, Bij Bosshardt's garden currently grows mint for tea. If more volunteers are recruited, they could expand to grow vegetables.

Challenges and Skepticism:

Some participants expressed skepticism about volunteer gardening projects, citing previous failed attempts. A lack of volunteers, insufficient appreciation, and limited time are common issues that prevent such initiatives from succeeding.

4. Accessibility and Affordability of Organic Products

Organic Products in Supermarkets:

Organic products are available in certain supermarkets, but they remain more expensive than conventional products. Participants wondered if Moroccan or Turkish supermarkets sell organic products. Although their produce may be grown without pesticides, it is often not labeled as organic.

Interest in Organic Food

There is a range of opinions about organic food. Some participants are indifferent, while others value it, particularly if it's fresh and GMO-free. However, organic products, even in canned form, aren't always affordable, and variety can be an issue.

Too Good to Go

Participants have used the Too Good to Go app to purchase discounted products from stores like Ekoplaza. However, some dislike the lack of choice in what they receive, particularly those with allergies or food preferences.

5. Discounted and Subsidized Organic Groceries

Pilot Extension:

There is a suggestion to extend the ongoing pilot project offering subsidized organic groceries to other neighborhoods, like Rivierenwijk. A manual is developed to allow other organizations to replicate the project and gather data for joint recommendations to the municipality. The manual is attached to Annexure.

Limited Organic Options at Food Banks:

The food bank rarely offers organic options, leaving clients who prefer organic food with limited choices.

7. Cultural and Organic Food Labels

Organic vs. Halal:

In the local community, the "Halal" label is often more valued than "organic," although one participant raised doubts about the reliability of the halal certification process. Others questioned whether all products labeled as organic truly meet the required standards, and there is some confusion about what qualifies as organic.

Health Concerns:

There are concerns about unconventional ingredients, such as insects, being introduced into processed foods like chocolate and candy. One participant prefers homemade treats and believes that Turkish and Moroccan shops offer safer alternatives.

Concluding the Voucher action:

The trial at Bij Bosshardt revealed strong interest in sustainable and organic food but also uncovered key barriers such as affordability, convenience, awareness, and accessibility that limit participants' access to these options. Despite these challenges, community members offered practical suggestions that present promising solutions, such as expanding the voucher program through partnerships, introducing

mobile organic markets, and adjusting the U-pas benefits to cover organic groceries. These ideas, coming directly from the people affected, highlight potential pathways to making organic food more accessible and culturally relevant.

This trial provided a detailed, on-the-ground view of both the obstacles and possible solutions. Not only has it illuminated the specific challenges participants face, but it has also offered viable ideas that could spark dialogue among diverse stakeholders from policymakers to local businesses. Importantly, the trial also brought diverse perspectives to light, allowing us to understand how we can support and implement these solutions to make Utrecht a more sustainable city. By combining these insights with collaborative action from stakeholders, we can address specific challenges, foster cultural inclusivity, and work toward a greener, healthier future for all Utrecht residents.

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Annexure

Manual for a trial of subsidized organic groceries

Ineke Malsch, 9/6/2024, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

In the citizens' initiative [Duurzaam Utrecht 2030](#) we organize sustainable living from the bottom up. We visit fellow citizens with a small budget in community centres where they feel at home, and ask how they already live sustainably themselves, what they would like more and what is holding them back. We regularly hear that people would like to eat organic or sustainable food, but that those groceries are usually too expensive. In the autumn of 2022, environmental science students at the HAS University of Applied Sciences in Den Bosch developed various proposals to bring sustainable fruit and vegetables from local growers to a distribution point in Lunetten and distribute them to local residents on a tight budget. Residents responded that they would like to choose for themselves, and suggested handing out vouchers with which they could buy organic food ([Van Eijk et al. 2022](#)). To better understand what the wishes of the target group were, we did a trial in which we handed out monthly vouchers in the Weggeefwinkel Lunetten in the fall of 2023, with which people could try out organic groceries. We collected and analysed the responses, presented our conclusions and recommendations to the participants and representatives of the organisations involved, and presented the recommendations in a public workshop ([Fedcenko, 2024](#)). We submitted specific recommendations for the municipality of Utrecht as [petition](#) to the municipal council, at which the mayor sent a formal [Reply Letter](#). In Lunetten, we are working in consultation with residents and organisations on follow-up steps, including a [Cookbook project](#). To find out whether people in another neighbourhood have the same wishes, we repeated the trial with subsidised organic groceries in a slightly modified form on [Kanaleneiland](#). We are also trying to involve other organisations in a joint roadmap for organic food with a small budget for 2030. People in several other neighbourhoods have already asked if we can carry out a similar trial in their neighbourhood. Because the goal of Duurzaam Utrecht 2030 is to get as many organizations as possible on board with a movement towards sustainable living from the bottom up, in which care for each other and the earth is combined, we prefer to publish this manual, with which interested organizations and individuals can do a similar trial themselves in their own neighborhood. We would then like to share the results and combine them into joint conclusions, recommendations and actions to influence the policy of the municipality and other relevant organisations. Are you interested? By all means, get started, but keep us posted. If you have any questions, we'd be happy to answer them.

Step 1: Train the team

Make sure that all researchers who hand out vouchers and collect responses are trained in interviews, social science research and ethics, and are aware of the rules for the participation of vulnerable people in social science research, and of rules for the protection of personal data. Read more about this in <https://www.utwente.nl/en/bms/research/forms-and-downloads/code-of-ethics-for-research-in-the-social-and-behavioural-sciences-dsw.pdf>

Step 2: Find partners in the area

Just handing out coupons on the street that allow random local residents to buy organic food elsewhere is a recipe for failure. Chances are, you'll never hear from the recipients again. Therefore, take the time to find a community center or walk-in where people with a small budget regularly come, for example at a weekly coffee morning or to pick up or drop off items at a giveaway shop. Talk to the responsible organization and ask for permission to hand out vouchers and collect responses a number of times in a row. Make sure that shops or vegetable gardens where people can buy organic groceries with the vouchers handed out are within walking distance, and make sure they cooperate with you. We used subsidies to buy vouchers, but you may be able to persuade providers to make (part of) them available for free. To give people freedom of choice, it helps to have at least two different providers participate. Experience shows that distance and accessibility make a big difference. Vouchers from providers that were closer were clearly more popular than those that required people to walk or cycle a little further.

Step 3: Announce the action

Visit at least once in advance to get to know the visitors and clearly explain what you are going to do and why, and what people will gain from it. Also announce the action in the (social) media, put up posters and ask the organization to inform their visitors.

Step 4: the questionnaire

Make a short questionnaire explaining the trial, when it is, what you are going to do with the results, that people are free whether they want to participate or not and can stop at any time, and that participation is completely anonymous. Hand out that questionnaire to everyone who wants a voucher, and also give a verbal explanation. Depending on the background of visitors, it may help to offer the questionnaire in their native language. We only handed out the questionnaires on paper, but participants suggested that it might work better to also create an online survey that people can find via a QR code. People for whom Dutch is not their mother tongue may then be able to answer in more detail in their own language and automatically translate their answer into Dutch. Our questionnaire can be found in the attachment. Feel free to adjust the questions as you see fit.

Step 5: Hand out vouchers

In consultation with the people responsible for the walk-in, join us for coffee and tell visitors clearly what you are coming to do, why, what they can do with the voucher, what you expect from them and what you will do with their reactions. Then wait to see if people ask for a voucher, and don't insist. Be patient, and remember that you are a guest, and that the visitors do not necessarily want to cooperate. Give everyone who receives a voucher the questionnaire with an explanation, and ask them to fill it in and hand it in to you or the team of the walk-in. Tell them which dates and times you will be coming again. Answer visitors' questions kindly and politely.

Step 6: Collect verbal and written responses

If the shop where participants can use the vouchers is close to the distribution point, some will fill out the questionnaire and hand it in immediately, but most will need time to do so. Ask the venue's team to take completed questionnaires in between handouts, or tell participants when you'll be back, and that they can hand in the questionnaire then. Also talk to participants who prefer to respond verbally, or who want to share a more extensive story. Listen and take notes anonymously. Not everyone will respond, and that's not a problem, participation is voluntary, and people can withdraw at any time.

Step 7: Publish reports of each voucher distribution campaign

After each voucher distribution, write a report in which you incorporate the responses, publish it online (or send the report to ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl asking them to post the report on <https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/en-gb/bioboodschappen>). Don't forget to also send the report to the team of the location where you are conducting the trial with the request to share it with visitors.

Step 8: Analyze the results and write draft conclusions and recommendations

Make an analysis of the products that people have bought with the vouchers, what they thought of them, and their wishes and suggestions for a follow-up, in which people with a small budget in the neighbourhood can buy or receive organic or sustainable food more often. Compare these results with those of the trials in Lunetten and Kanaleneiland, and with similar initiatives elsewhere. Draw preliminary conclusions and come up with recommendations for people and organizations in the neighborhood, the municipality and politicians, shopkeepers and organizations that are committed to poverty alleviation, health and environmental protection, and others you want to involve in a follow-up.

Step 9: discuss the draft conclusions and recommendations with the target group

Before finalizing your report, it is important to discuss your draft conclusions and recommendations with participants who want to discuss them with you. To do this, go back to the location where you handed out the vouchers. Emphasize that participation is voluntary and give people who participate an appropriate volunteer allowance as a thank you. Incorporate the responses into the draft report and send the result to the organizers.

Step 10: Discuss the draft conclusions and recommendations with partners

To increase the chance that follow-up steps will be taken after the trial, it is important to talk to representatives of organizations that you want to get involved in a step-by-step plan for follow-up activities in the neighborhood, city and other places. Organize a workshop in which you collect reactions to the results and especially the feasibility of the recommendations. Incorporate the responses into the report and finalize the final report. Send the result to the participants.

Step 11: public presentation of the final report

Present the final report to politicians, representatives of partner organisations, as many participants, journalists and fellow citizens as possible. For example, we organised a public presentation in the Dom Church at the end of 2023, and presented an official petition to the city council in February 2024. In consultation with you, we may be able to reach a larger audience and have more impact if we organize a joint public presentation of trials in several neighborhoods.

Annex: questionnaire

- 1) What did you buy with the voucher?

- 2) What do you think of the products you bought?

- 3) What did you think of the store where you used the voucher?

- 4) Do you want to buy organic or sustainable groceries more often? What do you need for this?

- 5) What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?

- 6) Do you have any other tips for us?

More information:

What do we do? We hand out vouchers with which you can buy organic and sustainable products yourself.

Would you like to answer the questions on this sheet anonymously? Or would you like to give us your opinion in a conversation? Participation is voluntary and anonymous. You can always withdraw immediately. We don't write your name down.

When do we hand out the vouchers? On Friday mornings 17 May, 14 June, 12 July, and 2 August 2024, between 10:00 and 12:00.

Where do we hand out the vouchers? While drinking coffee in Bij Bosshardt, Marco Pololaan 10 on Kanaleneiland.

Who is it for? Local residents with a small budget.

What do we do with your responses? We collect them anonymously in a report.

Debriefing: On Friday morning, September 13, 2024, we will discuss this report with you in Bij Bosshardt. We will incorporate your reactions and suggestions into the final report. Those who participate in this debriefing will receive a volunteer allowance.

In the autumn of 2024, we will publish the final report for the municipality of Utrecht and anyone who wants to know more. You'll also get a copy if you'd like.

News about the project appears on the website: <https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/> Would you like to know more or participate yourself? Please let me know: ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl.

MACHINE TRANSLATION FOR THE CONVENIENCE OF NON-DUTCH SPEAKERS – THE DUTCH VERSION IS OFFICIAL AND CORRECT.

Utrecht, 28 May 2024

Subject: Petition organic food

Dear Mrs. Malsch,

First of all, thank you very much for presenting your petition and the extensive survey you commissioned among residents of the Lunetten district. We appreciate your commitment to the city and your ability to think about solutions to this social challenge. In this letter, we would like to respond to the recommendations you make.

We endorse the importance of healthy and sustainable food, also for Utrecht residents who have less to spend. At the same time, financial resources are limited, so we cannot finance all the initiatives that we consider important. Below we indicate for each request what we already do and how we deal with your recommendation.

Food Pass Project:

We have followed the Food Pass project in Rotterdam with interest. The results of this project were partly positive, but affordability was the biggest issue. In Rotterdam, for example, the intention was to pay for the food budget from the proceeds of the food waste streams at supermarkets, social restaurants and other food retailers. That did not work out in this pilot period.

We also hear from our Stichting Voedselbank Utrecht that the residual flows in supermarkets are getting smaller and smaller.

In the new policy document on financial security of existence, the council has chosen to focus on the participation of children, safeguarding debt counselling and focusing on reaching as many low-income residents as possible. Thus, no funds are set aside for a food pass. That would also be very expensive, in Utrecht there are 23,000 households with an income below 125% (limit of the municipal poverty policy). Giving these households 40 euros a month, for example, costs more than 11 million euros on an annual basis.

If an initiative arises from the city, we would of course like to talk.

Involve shopkeepers' associations:

Utrecht has many shopkeepers' and entrepreneurs' associations, in which entrepreneurs network, collaborate and share knowledge and ideas. There are also many entrepreneurs who focus specifically on organic products and sustainability. For example, you can organize a partnership with merchants' associations to provide bonus cards for organic products. Perhaps the united shopkeepers would like to (co-)finance this from their Entrepreneurs' Fund in order to promote organic products and support individuals with a lower income together with other sustainable companies.

Expand sustainable activities in community centers:

The activities in the community centres managed by the municipality are organised by residents and users in collaboration with the municipality and welfare organisation DOCK. These parties aim for a weighted mix of activities depending on what is in demand. The self-managed community centres follow these frameworks but are responsible for their own activities. All community centres also offer spaces to social initiatives, such as the Food Bank, Digiwijs, language, movement and singing activities, etc. Sustainable Utrecht 2030 can also organise activities in consultation with the relevant community centres (or community rooms) to generate more attention for healthy and sustainable food. You may also be able to apply for a subsidy through the Initiatives Fund.

Tackle policy fragmentation:

Indeed, food is currently a theme in various policy areas such as climate, circular economy and health. Where the themes intersect, these domains work together. However, there is still no integrated ambition or approach for food. Due to the importance of the subject, we are currently investigating how we can give shape to this.

We hope to have informed you sufficiently. For more information, please contact Arie van Eck. We are curious about the results of a possible follow-up to your research.

Sincerely,

Mayor and aldermen of Utrecht,

Trial subsidised organic groceries Kanaleneiland, May-September 2024.

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips on what could be improved

Report of voucher campaign while drinking coffee in Bij Bosshardt, Marco Pololaan 10 Kanaleneiland, on May 17, 2024. By Ineke Malsch and Noor Ul Ain, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

On Friday morning, May 17, from 10 a.m. to 12 p.m., we handed out gift vouchers of 10 euros with which visitors could buy organic and sustainable food themselves. We handed out 22 vouchers from the packaging-free cart of Loos Utrecht, which was parked next to Bij Bosshardt especially for this campaign. 21 people bought something right away, one person saved the voucher to be able to buy something more expensive later. In addition, we handed out 9 vouchers from Utrecht Natuurlijk with which people could buy products from city farm Eilandsteede or vegetable garden Food for Good in Park Transwijk. Participants were given an A4 sheet explaining the trial with subsidised organic groceries and the questions about what they had bought and what they thought of it (see attachment). We had questionnaires in Dutch, English, Arabic and Dariya. On 3 and 5 May, we had already announced the trial to visitors of the coffee drinking and the Harbour meal.

Some visitors immediately gave their responses on 17 May, three of whom completed the questionnaires (see below). Other Notes:

- Loos Utrecht sells the products without packaging. It takes some getting used to taking that packaging with you. I already keep the organic waste separate, but I do throw away plastic waste every week. Products in the supermarket are wrapped in plastic. This cart goes back to the old days. Then the milkman came by with a milk churn and you got it in your own bottle. Now the milk comes in cardboard cartons with a plasticized layer. Why do they use virgin and not recycled plastic?
- I bought liquorice and candy (answer 1)
- At Lidl you can already buy fruit and vegetables packaging-free, but not anywhere else.
- Packaging-free is a smart idea, very special.
- I bought muesli, sunflower seeds and brown rice. The brown rice is almost gone, I use it daily. I add the sunflower seeds to the muesli.
- Amusing! I'm going to remember this.
- I have worked at Utrecht Natuurlijk in the hospitality industry and know the products they sell there.
- I am a vegetarian (answer 2). I really like the soup mix. I never buy pecans because they are too expensive. I bought raspberries with chocolate as a treat, I

don't buy them otherwise. I am very happy with it, it makes my day. The products are very beautiful, such as the soup for vegetarians. I have welfare, and not enough money. The Albert Heijn is too expensive.

- I help at the bird sanctuary, they also have a large vegetable garden. There is a new vegetable garden, which is an outdoor meeting point for people from different cultures. Volunteers get the vegetables for free, and they also get appreciation for what they do.
- Buying from the cart of Loos Utrecht went very smoothly. I'm very happy with pistachios, and I'm going to enjoy it tonight.

At the cart:

- I bought cashew nuts, and I think they are successful.
- I'm still saving up for mini wharf soaps.
- I want nuts, but which ones? A mix of salted and unsalted cashews?
- Nuts and chocolate
- I bought Cumin. Normally I take 1 kg with me from Morocco, but now it's gone. I put it on an egg, in the morning. It's healthy. Here a shop sells it, but 15 euros is too expensive.

On 14 June, 12 July and 2 August, we will be handing out more vouchers and talking to visitors. On 13 September, we will discuss the draft report with participants. We will publish the final report and give it to the municipality of Utrecht and organizations that can help to give residents of Kanaleneiland with a small budget the opportunity to eat organic or sustainable food more often.

Overview of the answers of 3 recipients of a voucher from Loos Utrecht (see also appendix 2):

Question	1	2	3
What did you buy with the voucher?	Licorice / candies	Soup mix, pecans, nuts, chocolate	Tea, cinnamon, almonds, crunch nuts & seeds, cacao nibs
What did you think of the products you bought?		Very nice products. Soup mix good idea	They are of excellent quality, very tasty and also good for the environment.

How did you find the store where you bought the voucher?	Community centre	Accident	By fine coincidence
Do you want to buy organic or sustainable products more often? What do you need for this?	Yes, support	Yes, more money	Yes, I would really like to. A bigger amount to spend.
What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?	Continue	Food bank	More offers on organic products or vouchers to spend on organic products.
Do you have any other tips for us?	No	Let us help with the vegetable garden as a volunteer	No, except that it's a super action that I'm very grateful for.

Trial with subsidised organic groceries on Kanaleneiland, May-September 2024.

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips on what could be improved

Report of voucher action while drinking coffee in [By Bosshardt](#), Marco Pololaan 10 Kanaleneiland, on 14 June 2024. By Ineke Malsch and Noor ul Ain, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

On Friday morning, June 14, from 10 a.m. to 12 p.m., we handed out gift vouchers of 10 euros with which visitors could buy organic and sustainable food themselves. We handed out 39 vouchers from the packaging-free cart of [Loos Utrecht](#), which was parked next to Bij Bosshardt especially for this action. 33 people bought something right away, others took a voucher for someone who couldn't be there that morning, or saved the voucher for next time. In addition, we handed out 9 vouchers from [Utrecht of course](#) with which people could buy products from the Eilandsteede city farm or the Food for Good vegetable garden in Park Transwijk. Participants were given an A4 sheet explaining the trial with subsidised organic groceries and the questions about what they had bought and what they thought of it (see attachment). We had questionnaires in Dutch, English, Arabic and Dariya, but people only took the Dutch questionnaires. Because we didn't have enough Dutch questionnaires, one person handed in the English questionnaire, with a Dutch answer.

Some visitors gave their responses on 14 June, and 23 people handed in the completed questionnaires on the spot, or had already handed them in to the people of the Salvation Army (see below). Together with the three questionnaires submitted on 17 May, 26 questionnaires have now been submitted, all for products from the cart of Loos Utrecht. Most people bought one or more types of nuts (21), and/or candy or biscuits (8). Other products mentioned were muesli or crunch (3), seeds (3), rice (2), tea (2), soup mix (1), soap (1), herbs (1), sprinkles (1) or quinoa (1). Most people were satisfied. Some shared suggestions for the municipality or other organisations to support people in affording organic or sustainable food more often.

Verbal responses:

- The muesli was tasty. The rice should cook for a long time. I want to do that in the morning and then put it away warm. We used to put the rice in a hay box, which would also be possible with this.
- The cart looks delicious.
- I get a discount at food4good, because I am a volunteer there.
- The walnuts and muesli are the most popular.
- I didn't see any tea on the cart. You can go to Food4good for that. I didn't ask why there was no tea.
- There is also licorice, natural licorice.
- There is no shop on Kanaleneiland that sells organic food (except for the large supermarkets). The nearest organic shop is Ekoplaza on the Amsterdamse straatweg.
- I come from a rural area, I am 55 years old. I used to be lucky with a grandfather who survived the Second World War. I was raised biologically. I can't afford the same

standard of living now. The basis has been good. My grandfather and father grew their own plums and strawberries. The greenhouse products taste like nothing. We had a wild plum tree. If you're brought up with that, you won't lose it. Take kale, I know the frost must have gone over it. My father used gooseberries and blackcurrants to make jam. In our village you had a bakery, and you came home with warm bread. I still remember the milk churn days, with a horse and cart. Acquaintances had goats, we milked them ourselves and drank the milk with a little cocoa. It's actually fancy. I've traveled through Europe. Somewhere along the border of Italy and France we ate delicious grapes. Dad had his own business. It was difficult to keep the standard of living high. I buy cheese from a good cheesemonger at the market. In the supermarket it tastes like nothing. I grumble about the food in the supermarket. I have a "gooise kaktong". I don't have it so good in the family. I don't drink, but if you're used to a good bottle of wine, you won't like cheap supermarket wine either. Before Chernobyl we had a vegetable garden, but not anymore. My grandfather had died, and my father didn't do it anymore.

- I know you from buurtbuik in Sterrenzicht. It's also delicious in the Nieuwe Jutter.
- I chose walnuts. Healthy nuts, not nuts, are almost priceless in the store. The quality of the cart is good.
- This voucher is a very nice gift. Tomorrow my children are coming to visit. I want to buy nuts to surprise them.
- Have you figured out what organic products they sell at Lidl? They have two types of honey, from spring and autumn. Honey is very healthy and delicious. [That depends on your tastes, someone else commented.] I examined the honey myself. How do you distinguish natural honey from sugar? Honey gives a prick in the throat, because of the taste of the honey. That's why it's very healthy. It comes directly from the bees. They sell it per two types. At the time, it cost 12 euros per kilo.
- I have a tip for the municipality, about the U-pas. Now you can put 75 euros on your OV-chipkaart and that leaves 45 euros. Most people can't take advantage of that amount, and can't use it with other agencies. Can the municipality allocate the 45 euros to organic products?

On 12 July and 2 August, we will be handing out more vouchers and talking to visitors. On 13 September, we will discuss the draft report with participants. We will publish the final report and give it to the municipality of Utrecht and organizations that can help to give residents of Kanaleneiland with a small budget the opportunity to eat organic or sustainable food more often.

Overview of the answers of recipients of a voucher from Loos Utrecht (see also appendix 2):

#	What did you buy with the voucher?	What do you think of the products you bought?	How did you find / what did you think of the store where you used the voucher?	Do you want to buy organic or sustainable products more often? What do you need for this?	What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?	Do you have any other tips for us?
4	cashew nuts, licorice, cookies					
5	soap	very good for the skin	terrific	sure	See question 4	50/50
6	Nuts without salt	Very good.	terrific. The Salvation Army is allowed to	sure	Offer more and small packages	stamp save and after 4x divide data voucher you can buy for 50% to 60%. You only pay a small amount
7	unsalted nuts	delicious.	The trolley at the Salvation Army: very easy and lots of choice	Yes. More points where you can buy it	See question 4	Given the short time that the cart has been present, maybe an extra seller
8	cashew nuts, chocolate almonds	delicious	small but mighty	Yes, a larger budget	U-pas budget expansion	
9	nuts.	good/tasty	amusing!	yes maybe	via the U-pas	No, not now.
10	chia seeds, almonds, pistachios.	satisfied	satisfied	yes please, not too expensive (cheap)	sponsoring the store so that I can buy the groceries cheaper	

11	Walnuts	of good quality	neat and a neat friendly gentleman	for my health	to accommodate something	no.
12	Walnuts	excellent	very nice and special	Yes definitely, but very pricey and little supply	More supply and larger supply	no
13	cashew nuts, licorice, cookies	they're good, yummy	You will be helped in a friendly way	yes. More shops.	Cooperate with this	
14	muesli natural, rice, sunflower seeds.	Muesli is very tasty. I still have to use the rice. I use the sunflower seeds in baking.	at the cart, very easy	I buy organic products in the supermarket when I get the chance, such as dairy, flour	An allowance for people with a low income would be desirable, healthy food leads to health and saves on illness and other costs.	entry in municipal directories.
15	muesli, nuts	good.	Nice cart, lots of choice	Yes, more offers in the area.	more supply.	
16	cashew, walnuts	very tasty	beautiful	It depends on the price!		
17	3 things kago and hazelnut	delicious	wonderful	yes like to eat and healthy.		
18	2 - Chokolata	delicious	wonderful	yes like to eat and healthy.		
19	Mixed nuts, ginger in chocolate and mango	Fresh and tasty, good combination	I thought it was a well-kept mobile stall	may, not necessary	a lot of people stand at markets or shopping malls.	No, it looked clear and neat. Good luck.

20	nuts	delicious	nice	I want to do it much more often	more money	Keep going
21	Salted cashew nuts	delicious.	at the Salvation Army	yes just not enough budget.	More budget	Discount vouchers
22	mixed nuts.	delicious.	at the Salvation Army	yes, but it doesn't work in terms of budget	Opening up the budget	Discount vouchers can be given
23	rice, sprinkles, nuts	beautiful.	beautiful	Money, The Shop	I already buy organic	think it's a good start
24	Rooibos tea + quinoa	Looks good!	Super nice shop, clear & you can see that these are organic products.	Yes, there may be more of these mobile shops!	Bid in Kanaleneiland on the market!	Maybe it would be nice to be at the market with a mobile shop, Friday. Super fun! A better environment starts with you!
25	pistachios, almonds, cashews	very good, tasty	neat, nice man	Yes, if it's cheaper.	making it cheaper by means of sponsoring	Multiple products
26	almond	I haven't tasted it yet	good	nuts	cheaper.	

Trial with subsidised organic groceries on Kanaleneiland, May-September 2024.

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips on what could be improved

Report of voucher action while drinking coffee in [By Bosshardt](#), Marco Pololaan 10 Kanaleneiland, on 12 July 2024. By Ineke Malsch and Noor ul Ain, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

On Friday morning, July 12, from 10 a.m. to 12 p.m., we handed out gift vouchers of 10 euros with which visitors could buy organic and sustainable food themselves. We handed out 41 vouchers from the packaging-free cart of [Loos Utrecht](#), which was parked next to Bij Bosshardt especially for this action. In addition, we handed out 16 vouchers from [Utrecht of course](#) with which people could buy products from the Eilandsteede city farm or the Food for Good vegetable garden in Park Transwijk. So far, we have handed out a total of 102 vouchers from Loos and 34 vouchers from Utrecht Natuurlijk. Participants were given an A4 sheet explaining the trial with subsidised organic groceries and the questions about what they had bought and what they thought of it (see attachment). We had questionnaires in Dutch, English, Arabic and Dariya, but people only took the Dutch questionnaires, and an Arabic one.

Some visitors gave their reactions on 12 June, and 18 people handed in the completed questionnaires on the spot, or had already handed them in to the people of the Salvation Army (see below). Together with the 26 questionnaires that were submitted earlier, 44 questionnaires have been submitted so far, all for products from the cart of Loos Utrecht, and one person had also bought something from Eilandsteede. In addition to a voucher for Loos, several people also wanted a voucher for Eilandsteede. When the grandchildren come, they can use them in the petting zoo shop. As long as the stock of 16 vouchers was not yet exhausted, we gave everyone who asked for it a voucher from Eilandsteede. At the end of the morning we had to disappoint one more person.

Verbal reactions in conversation with Ineke:

- Can the u-pas also be used to buy organic food? The activities offered for u-pas holders are all with a subscription.
- Last time my children came on Saturday after the coupon campaign. I gave them the nuts, and they really liked them.
- Last time I bought a pricey little bottle of blueberry juice at Eilandsteede, herbal tea and something else. I paid an extra 5.50 euros. They are very good products. I didn't mind paying extra, but I can't always afford it. If I had to pay for it myself, I couldn't.
- I have iron deficiency. I always buy nuts and stuff. It's very good for me.
- I bought almond-nut mix. It's yummy. I've tasted it, it's healthy. It's a small shop, and a sweet boy who works there. I would like to buy it more often, but it is expensive and can't. I don't know what the church could do. Normally I buy offers at Lidl or Dirk. I

- don't want to pay taxes with a benefit. Last year I had to pay 1000 euros and this year 1300 euros. [IM: I gave a leaflet about advice on money matters from the municipality.]
- Inflation is 3.2%, was in the news last week. You can hardly do anything with the remainder of 45 euros on the U-pas (after 75 euros have been put on an OV-chipkaart). It can help if you can also pay with the U-pas at electronics and white goods stores. Or at Burger King or McDonalds, or if you get a discount on a trip for the day.
 - I have insurance from Zorg en Zekerheid through the municipality, with a discount, but I pay more than an acquaintance, who is chronically ill and is insured with a regular insurer.
 - I am a volunteer at community center De Nieuwe Jutter in Rivierenwijk. Can you also do a trial with subsidized organic groceries?
 - Many adolescents want to fit in with their friends. Parents can't always fulfill their wishes to buy nice clothes and stuff.
 - You should be able to pay with a u-pas at more hairdressers. The only one I know is in IJsselstein. That might help too.
 - If I eat walnuts, cashews or muesli, I can go to the toilet well.
 - I had bought pistachios, but they were not crispy, and no longer tasty, even if you heat them in the oven. The chocolates were tasty.
 - The pecans are nice and crispy.
 - In the store, the nuts are expensive.
 - Do they still have honey on Eilandsteede? That is not known, we are waiting for someone who regularly comes to Eilandsteede to tell us if there is honey.

Noor's Reflections

- It would be great if farmers could bring the produce directly from their farms to the community centres. In this way we not only eat healthier food but also support our local farmers.
- In Morocco, you can get a large quantity of prickly pears ("prikkelbare peren" in Dutch) for just 1 euro, while here in the supermarket, you get only four for the same price.
- In my country food carts make healthy options easy to find. Here, I have to travel a lot to get the same healthy choices.
- I really want to buy healthy food options but because of the price I choose the cheapest options instead.
- I would prefer to buy at packaging-free cart of Loos Utrecht because it is local and I would like to support the local products.
- Loos has all the ingredients commonly found in Morocco, so it is easy for me, as a person from Morocco to have plenty of options.
- I can find cheaper and more options at Dirk and Lidl, but I also like Loos because it is convenient and the food is healthier.
- It would be convenient to use a QR code instead of paper and pen for filling out options or giving answers. With a QR code, you can do it online with different language options, and it can be easily shared through WhatsApp. This could be useful for the next trial and might be more helpful.

Next steps

On 2 August, we will be handing out more vouchers and talking to visitors. On 13 September, we will discuss the draft report with participants. We will publish the final report and give it to the municipality of Utrecht and organizations that can help to give residents of Kanaleneiland with a small budget the opportunity to eat organic or sustainable food more often.

Overview of the answers of recipients of a voucher from Loos Utrecht:

#	What did you buy with the voucher?	What do you think of the products you bought?	How did you find / what did you think of the store where you used the voucher?	Do you want to buy organic or sustainable products more often? What do you need for this?	What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?	Do you have any other tips for us?
27	Figs	Tasty – food	beautiful	Maybe tomorrow. bought 1st time		
28	Cashew nuts. Mix nuts, almonds, hazelnuts, Brazil nuts	Delicious	Very nice and clear	I'm getting older. Perhaps with a discount.	Branding. Inquire through community centers.	
29	Coconut chips, sprinkles, couscous	Didn't like the 'square' sprinkles. (I prefer elongated)	Great service	Not too expensive, nearby	Make it more common – more in the 'regular' stores? Using subsidies to make it cheaper	-
30	Cinnamon almonds & coconut cubes with chocolate	Very, very tasty! Something I normally wouldn't choose but surprisingly like.	Very nice! Nice system. Can even be dry in the rain.	In this way, I would love to. Handy without plastic too.	Things like this, or a discount with U-pas.	No thank you! I am very happy with it.

31	Almond	Perfectly healthy	excellent	Honey	Helping for poor people	Don't think only for the rich
32	Almond	Good	Excellent	Honey	Low price	Thinking for poor people
33	Soap handmade	Very good	Very good	Stimulance		ID then you get 1 voucher
34	Pine kernel beans	Very healthy	Particularly good	Preferably with a discount	An allowance per ID	Coming to get everything without sacrificing any contribution and insisting at the (cart) store that the salesperson has to hurry
35	Allen entos tach	Good & tasty	Good and clear	Yes, more often these kinds of mobile shops	Offering more alternatives like this	
36	Cashew nuts, almonds and chocolate almonds	Delicious! All look good.	Super fun and clear.	Yes. Even more coupons!	At various places in the district.	More organic

37	Cashew nuts, mix nuts, quinoa, muesli	Looks good!	Nice, uncluttered, cute.	Yes, definitely! I would like to eat healthier, but it is often unaffordable for me. It would be nice if it became more accessible.	Standing in different places and supporting the residents financially.	More organic. Connecting farmers and local residents.
38	Mixed nuts	Good	Good	Yes, visit more often	Making it attractive	-
39	Pistachios, hazelnuts	Good	Good	Yes.		
40	Whole grain penne, unsalted cashew nuts, herbal tea	I think they are good products.	With the cart, a wide range.	Yes, I choose what is affordable for me.	Support.	Not now.
41	Pecan nuts	Tasty and they made cookies with it	Good	Sometimes money is an issue	I don't know!	!
42	Pecan nuts	Delicious	Good	Sometimes more money	!	!

43	Walnuts	Excellent	Fun and special	If there's a store, definitely	Opening Stores	This is well taken care of.
44	Nuts	Delicious	Very useful	Fruit and vegetables	Or organic products may be involved in u-pas card.	-

Overview of the answers of recipients of a voucher from Eilandsteede (bought something from both Loos and Eilandsteede):

#	What did you buy with the voucher?	What do you think of the products you bought?	How did you find / what did you think of the store where you used the voucher?	Do you want to buy organic or sustainable products more often? What do you need for this?	What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?	Do you have any other tips for us?
29	apple juice	Apple juice was tasty	Great service	Not too expensive, nearby	Make it more common – more in the 'regular' stores? Using subsidies to make it cheaper	-

Trial with subsidised organic groceries on Kanaleneiland, May-September 2024.

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips on what could be improved

Report of voucher campaign while drinking coffee in [Bij Bosshardt](#), Marco Pololaan 10 Kanaleneiland, on August 2, 2024. By Ineke Malsch and Noor Ul Ain, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

On Friday morning, August 2, 2024 from 10 a.m. to 12 p.m., we handed out gift vouchers of 10 euros with which visitors could buy organic and sustainable food themselves. We handed out 46 vouchers from the packaging-free cart of [Loos Utrecht](#), which was parked next to Bij Bosshardt especially for this action. So far, we have handed out a total of 148 vouchers from Loos and 34 vouchers from Utrecht Natuurlijk. Participants were given an A4 sheet explaining the trial with subsidised organic groceries and the questions about what they had bought and what they thought of it (see attachment). We had questionnaires in Dutch, English, Arabic and Dariya, but people only took the Dutch questionnaires.

Some visitors gave their responses on 2 August, and 22 people handed in the completed questionnaires on the spot (some for 2 or 3 people at a time), or had already handed them in to the people of the Salvation Army (see below). Together with the 44 questionnaires that had already been submitted, 66 questionnaires have been submitted so far, all for products from the cart of Loos Utrecht, and one person had also bought something from Eilandsteede.

Verbal reactions in conversation with Ineke:

- A gentleman picked up the conversation about the u-pas from last time. The problem with the u-pas is: if you take out a subscription with u-pascredit, you are also stuck with it the following year. He doesn't want that. But with the 45 euros credit that remains after you have put 75 euros on an OV-chipcard, there is little else you can do. He would rather spend it on organic food or something else useful, or on fresh fruits and vegetables.
- If the U-pas decides to do a test with organic food, Loos Utrecht is willing to cooperate.
- To my remark that I thought there was no vegetable garden on Kanaleneiland, a lady responded that there is a neighbourhood vegetable garden, the Alexander Garden. There are vegetable gardens for children. It is between the Alexander de Grotelaan and the Columbuslaan. Neighbourhood children have a garden there. The garden actually belongs to her children, but she does most of the work there.
- A gentleman responded that every resident is entitled to their own garden of 1.5x1.5 meters. There they can plant whatever they want. His neighbour has one, but he doesn't because he can't take good care of plants.
- On the website of [buurtnatuur030.nl](#) There are 4 green initiatives on Kanaleneiland:
 - o Local residents adopt public gardens and tree mirrors between the flats on Alexander de Grotelaan

- A food forest has been created for children at the Schateiland primary school
- On Amerikalaan, local residents keep track of a tree mirror cluster
- At the Power Station, local residents keep a vertical garden in containers
- A lady has her own vegetable garden in Nieuwegein
- A gentleman asked where he could use the previously handed out vouchers from Utrecht Natuurlijk. I referred him to the Petting Zoo in Transwijk Park. He had been there before.
- In the garden next to Bij Bosshardt, organic mint is currently growing in containers with clean soil. They make their own tea from this. If the soil is not contaminated, and there are volunteers who want to garden, there could also be a small vegetable garden. At the moment, there are no concrete plans
- There is not yet a good overview of organizations that are active in social justice or green spaces in the Kanaleneiland district or other parts of the city. It would be nice to have an overview in the form of an online social map, although organizations sometimes disappear again. There is now a network Thuis in je wijk of the Network Informal Care Utrecht NIZU.nl. This is an initiative of organizations that discuss what they can do together. Even if announcements are put up or flyers are placed on a table, not everyone gets it.
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Noor's musings

- One individual suggested that the organic grocery initiative should be extended over a longer period and expanded to other neighborhoods in Utrecht to gather more comprehensive data.
- Another person emphasized the importance of convenience, noting that they are unaware of the locations of organic shops in the city and find Loos Utrecht particularly convenient for purchasing food.
- Many individuals gave positive feedback on the food they purchased with the voucher, with some mentioning that these products are available in their home countries, making it enjoyable to buy them here with the voucher.
- There was also a recommendation for organic stores to provide vouchers or discount cards to low-income individuals, making these healthier options more accessible.

Next steps

On 13 September, we will discuss the draft report with participants. We will publish the final report and give it to the municipality of Utrecht and organizations that can help to give residents of Kanaleneiland with a small budget the opportunity to eat organic or sustainable food more often.

Overview of the answers of recipients of a voucher from Loos Utrecht:

#	What did you buy with the voucher?	What do you think of the products you bought?	How did you find / what did you think of the store where you used the voucher?	Do you want to buy organic or sustainable products more often? What do you need for this?	What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?	Do you have any other tips for us?
45	Red rice	Healthy	Nice, good	Vegetables and meat	Low price	With u-pas low price
46+47	Almonds, mixed nuts, cashew nuts	Good	Perfect	Yes. More Stores	What's good for you is good for us.	
48+49+50	Flaxseed, cashew nuts, black rice, granola, nuts, lentils	Delicious	Super fun! Clear and a friendly man	Yes, definitely. That it becomes more affordable.	Give vouchers.	Do this more often.
51	Chocolate almonds, chocolate raspberries, pine nuts, coconut, granola chocolate and cinnamon almonds	Lovely, look good.	Clear	Yes, these vouchers	Handing out vouchers	no

52	Chocolate raspberries, chocolate almonds, cinnamon almonds	Good	Super fun and clear	Yes, <u>these vouchers!</u>	Handing out vouchers	no
53	Nuts	Very tasty	Very nice	No, organic is too expensive	The price should be low	Think of poor people
54	Peanuts pistachios	Good	Excellent	Not familiar with the prod.	Don't know	Not really
55	Basic muesli, oat flakes, chocolate oat flakes	Good quality	Enjoyable	Yes, I buy organic products in the supermarket, I am selective about that.	Financially supporting, healthy products lead to health and reduce healthcare costs	Putting up posters in neighbourhoods
56	Almonds, tea, pistachio	Very nice / nice	Nice people	Certainly, more salary	Discounts, etc.	-
57	Pistachio and almond	Delicious	Nice nut bar	Yes, sometimes.	I don't know	No

58	Pistachio and Brazil nuts	Delicious	Nice nut bar	Yes, sometimes	I don't know	no
59	Brazil nuts	Delicious	Nice nut bar	Sometimes	I don't know	no
60	Pistachio and Brazil nuts	Delicious	Amusing	Yes, I already buy them, sometimes	I don't know	no
61	Walnuts	Excellent	Bij Bosshardt, nice surroundings	Yes	Mobile shop	no
62	Nuts	Delicious from experience	Good	Maybe so	Often, it's too expensive	No, not really
63	Cashews	Its good	good			
64	Pistachio and walnuts	Delicious	Very handy	Yes, it doesn't cut short		

65	Pistachio nuts	Delicious and lots	A nice invention: the nut cart	I can just do that	I bought organic pointed cabbage	no
66	Pecan nuts	Good	Amusing	More income	More frequent receipts	

Trial with subsidised organic groceries on Kanaleneiland, May-September 2024.

Try organic groceries yourself - Tell us what you think - And share your tips on what could be improved

Report of voucher campaign while drinking coffee in [Bij Bosshardt](#), Marco Pololaan 10 Kanaleneiland, on Monday 2 September 2024. By Ineke Malsch and Noor Ul Ain, ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl

On Monday morning, September 2, 2024 from 10 a.m. to 12 p.m., we handed out 10-euro gift vouchers that visitors could use to buy organic and sustainable food themselves. We handed out 38 vouchers for the packaging-free cart of [Loos Utrecht](#), which was parked next to Bij Bosshardt especially for this campaign. So far, we have handed out a total of 186 vouchers from Loos and 34 vouchers from Utrecht Natuurlijk. Participants were given an A4 sheet explaining the trial with subsidised organic groceries and the questions about what they had bought and what they thought of it (see attachment). We had questionnaires in Dutch, English, Arabic and Dariya, but people only took the Dutch questionnaires this time.

Some visitors gave their responses on 2 September, and 19 people handed in the completed questionnaires on the spot, or had already handed them in to the people of the Salvation Army (see below). Together with the 66 questionnaires that were submitted earlier, 85 questionnaires have been submitted so far, 84 for products from the cart of Loos Utrecht, of which one person had also bought something from Eilandsteede, plus one only for products from Eilandsteede.

Verbal reactions in conversation with Ineke:

- Someone asked what our findings were so far. We told them that we had discussed the suggestion to use part of the U-paste with the organization, but that this credit may not be used for food and drinks. There are meal providers who give U-pas holders a discount, but they do not receive any money from the U-pas.
- Someone had experience with this: once a week you can participate in a meal in various community centers, where U-pas holders get a discount. The meals are not necessarily organic. The lady herself had bought a lot of muesli at XENOS, where it was on sale. At LIDL they have a lot of organic pasta and eggs, potatoes, vegetables, fruit, garlic and onions. Also at Dirk they have a lot of organic, and ALDI too (I think). I never go to AH. Jumbo also has a rack with organic products, such as coffee. Lidl doesn't have organic coffee, Dirk does. I do buy organic oatmeal. Organic vegetables are sometimes overlooked. I don't eat organic meat, and I don't eat vegetarian products either.
- If you come for coffee at Bij Bosshardt on different days, you can meet different people.
- Loos could come more often. On Friday morning there is a market on Kanaleneiland.
- But the owner says that his cart is only allowed to be parked somewhere if there are customers around. Otherwise, he will have to drive on. He also needs permission from the ward board.
- If he was here for a regular afternoon, and you know when, that would help.

- Young people are more aware of organic food.
- People want organic food more often, but you can't afford it. E.g. pistachios are very healthy, but too expensive, so you buy peanuts or something. It's nice, but it has to be affordable. Everything is more expensive, not only food, but also fixed costs. Poor people can afford a handful of nuts a month, not a day, as is recommended.
- At the cart, men who wanted to buy something said: it's too expensive! That's why they asked for a second receipt.
- Suggestions for extending the trial: Hoograven.
- The range of organic food at the cart is accessible to people of all cultures and religions. It fits into different dietary requirements.
- I really enjoyed the voucher at Eilandsteede. They have delicious apple juice, and it's a lovely place.
- The cashews I had bought went stale quickly. You have to buy them packaged, otherwise they won't stay fresh. Other products are fine. Brown rice should be boiled for 45 minutes. That's tricky, I prefer short-boiling rice, and I don't like the rice from the cart. You only have to cook the organic rice from the store for 15 minutes. As a solution, I cooked a large portion of rice and put the pan to bed. I used to work in an organic restaurant. We cooked the rice for 10 minutes in the morning, then she continued to cook in the hay box. We also cooked beans like this, I have the experience that that goes well, it stayed warm all day. If you have to cook rice for 45 minutes when you're preparing dinner at night, it's tricky. The rice could be better. I used to work at the Groene Waterman. That was a shop and restaurant, which used to be located on the Springweg. Then they went to the Zadelstraat, and now they are no longer there. I miss flour products on the cart. Maybe they have them in the store? I like to buy organic flour, and have started to bake my own sourdough bread. I have the opportunity to do so now, not when I was working. Back then, I used to buy alinson bread at AH. Someone warned me about dark brown bread, which contains food coloring. It's not healthier. I'm in favor of whole grain. Ten years ago, I made my own sourdough bread. It takes time and money if you want to make organic and healthy choices. I was given a recipe to make sourdough bread from organic rye flour. That was just on sale. I also bought cheap muesli at XENOS. It takes more effort, you have to go to different stores, and you can't buy everything from the same supermarket. Healthy food is important. A suggestion for a follow-up is to hand out recipes, and cook together. Ask if there is any interest in this on 13 September. I like to bake my own bread. Most bread in the store isn't the best.
- Is there interest in giving cooking lessons: bake your own bread with sourdough?
- You can also find the recipe and instructions on google. The explanation is step-by-step: make sourdough. Wait 8 hours, etc. When you have a family, it's harder. If you live alone, bake 2 loaves of bread and put one in the freezer. You can also make kefir yourself. You can buy it at ekoplaza. I have a year of experience at a vegetarian restaurant. That's also where I learned tricks, how to cook for 100 people. The restaurant De Werfkring on the Oude Gracht also used to have a shop in the Vinkenburgstraat.

- I am interested in participating in a follow-up project, for example cooking together and trying out recipes with a group. I think that would be fun. I would like to know how to prepare quinoa and bulgur.

Noor's musings

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Next steps

We will discuss the draft report with participants on 13 September 2024 in Bij Bosshardt. We will publish the final report and give it to the municipality of Utrecht and organizations that can help to give residents of Kanaleneiland with a small budget the opportunity to eat organic or sustainable food more often.

Overview of the answers of recipients of a voucher from Loos Utrecht:

#	What did you buy with the voucher?	What do you think of the products you bought?	How did you find / what did you think of the store where you used the voucher?	Do you want to buy organic or sustainable products more often? What do you need for this?	What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?	Do you have any other tips for us?
67	Brazil nuts, muesli	It looks very tasty. Tomorrow morning I'm going to taste the muesli in my yogurt.	Nice, friendly and well-organized	Yes. A little more time to go to the green store.		Make it cheaper, and I have to eat more seasonally myself.
68	Walnuts, brown rice, cashew nuts	Amusing	Good	Yes. A shop on Kanaleneiland.	Spread the word	No.
69	Walnuts	Good	Good, nice	I don't know	?	Not really.
70	Walnuts	Good	Amusing	More budget	Reduce VAT, increase income	

71	Brazil nuts	Delicious	Favourable	Yes	?	-
72	Pistachio + walnuts	Delicious	Favourable	Yes	?	-
73	Detergent, oil and toothpaste	I'm going to try them out, I don't know yet	Friendly employee, nice stuff	Yes, please, that they become a little cheaper	Making it more accessible (e.g. in neighbourhoods such as Kanaleneiland)	
74	Nuts		Nice, good planning	No, not normally. Too expensive, but healthy.	Occasionally in AH and supermarket	
75	Bulgur, quinoa, couscous	It's nice that there are organic products	I missed flour	Yes, I'm on a low budget, so I can't do it all the time	Affordable through offers, e.g.	Nuts are not such a success, I prefer to buy them packaged.
77	Muesli	Good	Nice -> the cart	More offer	Make it better known, more stores	

78	Brazil nuts + pistachio	Delicious	Amusing	Yes, but then I have to have enough money	Something like that, where I can buy organic products with a voucher	No.
79	Brazil nuts	Delicious	The nut bar is nice	I've been doing that sometimes	I don't know	No
80	Yellow split peas and walnuts	Good	Good idea	I buy all kinds of things, because I use it.	Sell cheaper	More stalls
81	Cashew nuts / chocolate nuts	A grade between 1-10: 7.5	Nice people, good products	Good Finances/Income	Food bank for organic products	no
82	Pistachio, mixed nuts	Perfect	Good	Yes, offers	Opening a store	No, that's fine.
83	Nuts, ginger	Totally awesome	Plenty of choices	The days and where	More places	Keep up the good work
84	Pistachio + mixed nuts	Delicious	Perfect, very happy with it	Yes. No money. Too little to buy that		No.

85	Pistachio + mixed nuts	Delicious!	Perfect, nice that this is possible!	Yes, but little budget due to benefits	Giving more budget	I am glad that this alternative exists.
oral	Almonds and turmeric	Delicious		I don't buy organic more often, it's a bit expensive. I can't afford the extra things you need.		

Overview of the answers of recipients of a voucher from Eilandsteede:

#	What did you buy with the voucher?	What do you think of the products you bought?	How did you find / what did you think of the store where you used the voucher?	Do you want to buy organic or sustainable products more often? What do you need for this?	What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?	Do you have any other tips for us?
76	Apple juice, syrup	Good	Could be a bit more extensive	More points of sale	More offer	

Appendix 1: More information about the subsidised organic grocery trial on Kanaleneiland, May-September 2024:

Ask:

- 1) What did you buy with the voucher?

- 2) What do you think of the products you bought?

- 3) How did you find the store where you used the voucher?

- 4) Do you want to buy organic or sustainable groceries more often? What do you need for this?

- 5) What can the municipality of Utrecht or another organization do to help you buy organic groceries?

- 6) Do you have any other tips for us?

More information:

What do we do? We hand out vouchers with which you can buy organic and sustainable products yourself.

Would you like to answer the questions on this sheet anonymously? Or would you like to give us your opinion in a conversation? Participation is voluntary and anonymous. You can always withdraw immediately. We don't write your name down.

When do we hand out the vouchers? On Friday mornings 17 May, 14 June, 12 July, and 2 August 2024, between 10:00 and 12:00.

Where do we hand out the vouchers? While drinking coffee in Bij Bosshardt, Marco Pololaan 10 on Kanaleneiland.

Who is it for? Local residents with a small budget.

What do we do with your responses? We collect them anonymously in a report.

Debriefing: On Friday morning, September 13, 2024, we will discuss this report with you in Bij Bosshardt. We will incorporate your reactions and suggestions into the final report. Those who participate in this debriefing will receive a volunteer allowance.

In the autumn of 2024, we will publish the final report for the municipality of Utrecht and anyone who wants to know more. You'll also get a copy if you'd like.

News about the project appears on the website: <https://duurzaamutrecht2030.nl/> Would you like to know more or participate yourself? Please let me know: ineke@duurzaamutrecht2030.nl.